

Material Report

Project: D:\D\lesson\term8\rahsazi\project\tarahiroghomi_omd.dwg

Alignment: Alignment -bromd

Sample Line Group: s1

Start Sta: 0+000.000

End Sta: 22+869.084

	Area Type	Area	Inc.Vol.	Cum.Vol.
		Sq.m.	Cu.m.	Cu.m.
Station: 0+000.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	27.85	0.00	0.00
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	7.56	0.00	0.00
	topeka	0.31	0.00	0.00
	binder	0.31	0.00	0.00
	base	1.31	0.00	0.00
	subbase	4.53	0.00	0.00
Station: 0+050.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	45.40	1831.31	1831.31
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.25	195.22	195.22
	topeka	0.31	15.28	15.28
	binder	0.31	15.59	15.59
	base	1.31	65.50	65.50
	subbase	4.53	226.50	226.50
Station: 0+100.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	79.73	3128.18	4959.49
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.00	6.18	201.40
	topeka	0.31	15.28	30.56
	binder	0.31	15.59	31.19
	base	1.31	65.50	131.00
	subbase	4.53	226.50	453.00
Station: 0+150.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	0.00	1993.24	6952.73
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	84.91	2122.78	2324.18
	topeka	0.31	15.28	45.84
	binder	0.31	15.59	46.78
	base	1.31	65.50	196.50
	subbase	4.53	226.50	679.50
Station: 0+200.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	0.00	0.00	6952.73
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	520.80	15142.80	17466.97
	topeka	0.31	15.28	61.12
	binder	0.31	15.59	62.37
	base	1.31	65.50	262.00

	subbase	4.53	226.50	906.00
Station: 0+250.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	0.00	0.17	6952.90
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	551.47	26806.79	44273.76
	topeka	0.31	15.28	76.41
	binder	0.31	15.59	77.97
	base	1.31	65.50	327.50
	subbase	4.53	226.50	1132.50
Station: 0+300.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	0.00	0.17	6953.06
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	564.36	27895.77	72169.53
	topeka	0.31	15.28	91.69
	binder	0.31	15.59	93.56
	base	1.31	65.50	393.00
	subbase	4.53	226.50	1359.00
Station: 0+350.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	0.00	0.00	6953.06
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	858.78	35578.59	107748.12
	topeka	0.31	15.28	106.97
	binder	0.31	15.59	109.16
	base	1.31	65.50	458.50
	subbase	4.53	226.50	1585.50
Station: 0+400.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	0.00	0.00	6953.06
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	1317.09	54396.79	162144.91
	topeka	0.31	15.28	122.25
	binder	0.31	15.59	124.75
	base	1.31	65.50	524.00
	subbase	4.53	226.50	1812.00
Station: 0+450.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	0.00	0.00	6953.06
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	1755.87	76824.06	238968.97
	topeka	0.31	15.28	137.53
	binder	0.31	15.59	140.34
	base	1.31	65.50	589.50
	subbase	4.53	226.50	2038.50
Station: 0+500.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	0.00	0.00	6953.06
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	2322.17	101951.21	340920.18
	topeka	0.31	15.28	152.81
	binder	0.31	15.59	155.94
	base	1.31	65.50	655.00
	subbase	4.53	226.50	2265.00
Station: 0+550.000				

	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	0.00	0.00	6953.06
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	2687.15	125233.09	466153.28
	topeka	0.31	15.28	168.09
	binder	0.31	15.59	171.53
	base	1.31	65.50	720.50
	subbase	4.53	226.50	2491.50
Station: 0+600.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	0.00	0.00	6953.06
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	2948.11	140881.41	607034.68
	topeka	0.31	15.28	183.37
	binder	0.31	15.59	187.12
	base	1.31	65.50	786.00
	subbase	4.53	226.50	2718.00
Station: 0+650.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	0.00	0.00	6953.06
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	3148.06	152404.22	759438.90
	topeka	0.31	15.28	198.66
	binder	0.31	15.59	202.72
	base	1.31	65.50	851.50
	subbase	4.53	226.50	2944.50
Station: 0+700.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	0.00	0.00	6953.06
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	2561.73	142744.70	902183.60
	topeka	0.31	15.28	213.94
	binder	0.31	15.59	218.31
	base	1.31	65.50	917.00
	subbase	4.53	226.50	3171.00
Station: 0+750.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	0.00	0.00	6953.06
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	1601.40	104078.04	1006261.64
	topeka	0.31	15.28	229.22
	binder	0.31	15.59	233.91
	base	1.31	65.50	982.50
	subbase	4.53	226.50	3397.50
Station: 0+800.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	0.00	0.00	6953.06
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	378.33	49493.16	1055754.79
	topeka	0.31	15.28	244.50
	binder	0.31	15.59	249.50
	base	1.31	65.50	1048.00
	subbase	4.53	226.50	3624.00
Station: 0+850.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	484.81	12120.20	19073.26
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.00	9458.27	1065213.06

	topeka	0.31	15.28	259.78
	binder	0.31	15.59	265.09
	base	1.31	65.50	1113.50
	subbase	4.53	226.50	3850.50
Station: 0+900.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	796.75	32039.07	51112.33
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.00	0.00	1065213.06
	topeka	0.31	15.28	275.06
	binder	0.31	15.59	280.69
	base	1.31	65.50	1179.00
	subbase	4.53	226.50	4077.00
Station: 0+950.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	95.69	22311.17	73423.50
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.02	0.52	1065213.59
	topeka	0.31	15.28	290.34
	binder	0.31	15.59	296.28
	base	1.31	65.50	1244.50
	subbase	4.53	226.50	4303.50
Station: 1+000.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	0.00	2392.30	75815.80
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	92.67	2317.32	1067530.90
	topeka	0.31	15.28	305.62
	binder	0.31	15.59	311.88
	base	1.31	65.50	1310.00
	subbase	4.53	226.50	4530.00
Station: 1+050.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	289.71	7242.84	83058.64
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.00	2316.79	1069847.70
	topeka	0.31	15.28	320.91
	binder	0.31	15.59	327.47
	base	1.31	65.50	1375.50
	subbase	4.53	226.50	4756.50
Station: 1+100.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	947.38	30927.30	113985.94
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.00	0.00	1069847.70
	topeka	0.31	15.28	336.19
	binder	0.31	15.59	343.06
	base	1.31	65.50	1441.00
	subbase	4.53	226.50	4983.00
Station: 1+150.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	1284.26	55790.92	169776.86
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.00	0.00	1069847.70
	topeka	0.31	15.28	351.47
	binder	0.31	15.59	358.66

	base	1.31	65.50	1506.50
	subbase	4.53	226.50	5209.50
Station: 1+200.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	1165.31	61239.31	231016.16
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.00	0.00	1069847.70
	topeka	0.31	15.28	366.75
	binder	0.31	15.59	374.25
	base	1.31	65.50	1572.00
	subbase	4.53	226.50	5436.00
Station: 1+250.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	882.21	51188.04	282204.21
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.00	0.00	1069847.70
	topeka	0.31	15.28	382.03
	binder	0.31	15.59	389.84
	base	1.31	65.50	1637.50
	subbase	4.53	226.50	5662.50
Station: 1+300.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	416.96	32479.29	314683.50
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.00	0.00	1069847.70
	topeka	0.31	15.28	397.31
	binder	0.31	15.59	405.44
	base	1.31	65.50	1703.00
	subbase	4.53	226.50	5889.00
Station: 1+350.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	284.69	17541.46	332224.96
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.00	0.00	1069847.70
	topeka	0.31	15.28	412.59
	binder	0.31	15.59	421.03
	base	1.31	65.50	1768.50
	subbase	4.53	226.50	6115.50
Station: 1+400.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	169.10	11344.84	343569.79
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.00	0.00	1069847.70
	topeka	0.31	15.28	427.87
	binder	0.31	15.59	436.63
	base	1.31	65.50	1834.00
	subbase	4.53	226.50	6342.00
Station: 1+450.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	0.07	4229.28	347799.07
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	6.61	165.25	1070012.95
	topeka	0.31	15.28	443.16
	binder	0.31	15.59	452.22
	base	1.31	65.50	1899.50
	subbase	4.53	226.50	6568.50

Station: 1+500.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	0.00	1.79	347800.86
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	200.60	5180.17	1075193.12
	topeka	0.31	15.28	458.44
	binder	0.31	15.59	467.81
	base	1.31	65.50	1965.00
	subbase	4.53	226.50	6795.00
Station: 1+550.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	0.00	0.00	347800.86
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	339.05	13491.15	1088684.27
	topeka	0.31	15.28	473.72
	binder	0.31	15.59	483.41
	base	1.31	65.50	2030.50
	subbase	4.53	226.50	7021.50
Station: 1+600.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	0.00	0.00	347800.86
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	195.40	13361.34	1102045.61
	topeka	0.31	15.28	489.00
	binder	0.31	15.59	499.00
	base	1.31	65.50	2096.00
	subbase	4.53	226.50	7248.00
Station: 1+650.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	0.00	0.17	347801.03
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	71.20	6665.13	1108710.73
	topeka	0.31	15.28	504.28
	binder	0.31	15.59	514.59
	base	1.31	65.50	2161.50
	subbase	4.53	226.50	7474.50
Station: 1+700.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	0.00	0.17	347801.20
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	4.48	1892.12	1110602.86
	topeka	0.31	15.28	519.56
	binder	0.31	15.59	530.19
	base	1.31	65.50	2227.00
	subbase	4.53	226.50	7701.00
Station: 1+750.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	28.25	706.19	348507.39
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.00	112.16	1110715.01
	topeka	0.31	15.28	534.84
	binder	0.31	15.59	545.78
	base	1.31	65.50	2292.50
	subbase	4.53	226.50	7927.50
Station: 1+800.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	58.04	2157.15	350664.54

	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.00	0.07	1110715.08
	topeka	0.31	15.28	550.12
	binder	0.31	15.59	561.38
	base	1.31	65.50	2358.00
	subbase	4.53	226.50	8154.00
Station: 1+850.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	0.00	1450.96	352115.50
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	56.41	1410.31	1112125.39
	topeka	0.31	15.28	565.41
	binder	0.31	15.59	576.97
	base	1.31	65.50	2423.50
	subbase	4.53	226.50	8380.50
Station: 1+900.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	0.00	0.00	352115.50
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	194.93	6283.57	1118408.96
	topeka	0.31	15.28	580.69
	binder	0.31	15.59	592.56
	base	1.31	65.50	2489.00
	subbase	4.53	226.50	8607.00
Station: 1+950.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	0.00	0.09	352115.59
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	78.01	6823.60	1125232.56
	topeka	0.31	15.28	595.97
	binder	0.31	15.59	608.16
	base	1.31	65.50	2554.50
	subbase	4.53	226.50	8833.50
Station: 2+000.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	0.00	0.09	352115.68
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	154.72	5818.32	1131050.89
	topeka	0.31	15.28	611.25
	binder	0.31	15.59	623.75
	base	1.31	65.50	2620.00
	subbase	4.53	226.50	9060.00
Station: 2+050.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	0.00	0.00	352115.68
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	498.00	16318.00	1147368.89
	topeka	0.31	15.28	626.53
	binder	0.31	15.59	639.34
	base	1.31	65.50	2685.50
	subbase	4.53	226.50	9286.50
Station: 2+100.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	0.00	0.00	352115.68
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	783.13	32028.20	1179397.09
	topeka	0.31	15.28	641.81

	binder	0.31	15.59	654.94
	base	1.31	65.50	2751.00
	subbase	4.53	226.50	9513.00
Station: 2+150.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	0.00	0.00	352115.68
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	682.61	36643.44	1216040.53
	topeka	0.31	15.28	657.09
	binder	0.31	15.59	670.53
	base	1.31	65.50	2816.50
	subbase	4.53	226.50	9739.50
Station: 2+200.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	0.00	0.00	352115.68
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	517.67	30006.98	1246047.51
	topeka	0.31	15.28	672.37
	binder	0.31	15.59	686.13
	base	1.31	65.50	2882.00
	subbase	4.53	226.50	9966.00
Station: 2+250.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	0.00	0.00	352115.68
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	347.04	21617.62	1267665.13
	topeka	0.31	15.28	687.66
	binder	0.31	15.59	701.72
	base	1.31	65.50	2947.50
	subbase	4.53	226.50	10192.50
Station: 2+300.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	0.00	0.00	352115.68
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	140.19	12180.75	1279845.88
	topeka	0.31	15.28	702.94
	binder	0.31	15.59	717.31
	base	1.31	65.50	3013.00
	subbase	4.53	226.50	10419.00
Station: 2+350.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	0.18	4.50	352120.19
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	183.34	8088.33	1287934.21
	topeka	0.31	15.28	718.22
	binder	0.31	15.59	732.91
	base	1.31	65.50	3078.50
	subbase	4.53	226.50	10645.50
Station: 2+400.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	0.00	4.50	352124.69
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	432.75	15402.33	1303336.54
	topeka	0.31	15.28	733.50
	binder	0.31	15.59	748.50
	base	1.31	65.50	3144.00

	subbase	4.53	226.50	10872.00
Station: 2+450.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	0.95	23.79	352148.48
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	81.96	12867.76	1316204.30
	topeka	0.31	15.28	748.78
	binder	0.31	15.59	764.09
	base	1.31	65.50	3209.50
	subbase	4.53	226.50	11098.50
Station: 2+500.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	251.93	6321.97	358470.45
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.00	2048.91	1318253.21
	topeka	0.31	15.28	764.06
	binder	0.31	15.59	779.69
	base	1.31	65.50	3275.00
	subbase	4.53	226.50	11325.00
Station: 2+550.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	848.23	27503.90	385974.35
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.00	0.00	1318253.21
	topeka	0.31	15.28	779.34
	binder	0.31	15.59	795.28
	base	1.31	65.50	3340.50
	subbase	4.53	226.50	11551.50
Station: 2+600.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	1278.46	53167.19	439141.53
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.00	0.00	1318253.21
	topeka	0.31	15.28	794.62
	binder	0.31	15.59	810.88
	base	1.31	65.50	3406.00
	subbase	4.53	226.50	11778.00
Station: 2+650.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	1429.85	67707.81	506849.34
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.00	0.00	1318253.21
	topeka	0.31	15.28	809.91
	binder	0.31	15.59	826.47
	base	1.31	65.50	3471.50
	subbase	4.53	226.50	12004.50
Station: 2+700.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	1319.21	68726.49	575575.83
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.00	0.00	1318253.21
	topeka	0.31	15.28	825.19
	binder	0.31	15.59	842.06
	base	1.31	65.50	3537.00
	subbase	4.53	226.50	12231.00
Station: 2+750.000				

	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	1128.58	61194.55	636770.38
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.00	0.00	1318253.21
	topeka	0.31	15.28	840.47
	binder	0.31	15.59	857.66
	base	1.31	65.50	3602.50
	subbase	4.53	226.50	12457.50
Station: 2+800.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	311.27	35996.07	672766.46
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.00	0.00	1318253.21
	topeka	0.31	15.28	855.75
	binder	0.31	15.59	873.25
	base	1.31	65.50	3668.00
	subbase	4.53	226.50	12684.00
Station: 2+850.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	6.89	7953.88	680720.34
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	5.22	130.47	1318383.69
	topeka	0.31	15.28	871.03
	binder	0.31	15.59	888.84
	base	1.31	65.50	3733.50
	subbase	4.53	226.50	12910.50
Station: 2+900.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	0.00	172.20	680892.54
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	193.51	4968.22	1323351.91
	topeka	0.31	15.28	886.31
	binder	0.31	15.59	904.44
	base	1.31	65.50	3799.00
	subbase	4.53	226.50	13137.00
Station: 2+950.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	0.00	0.00	680892.54
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	314.40	12697.82	1336049.72
	topeka	0.31	15.28	901.59
	binder	0.31	15.59	920.03
	base	1.31	65.50	3864.50
	subbase	4.53	226.50	13363.50
Station: 3+000.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	0.00	0.00	680892.54
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	421.24	18391.08	1354440.80
	topeka	0.31	15.28	916.87
	binder	0.31	15.59	935.63
	base	1.31	65.50	3930.00
	subbase	4.53	226.50	13590.00
Station: 3+003.965				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	0.00	0.00	680892.54
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	429.20	1686.20	1356127.00

	topeka	0.31	1.21	918.09
	binder	0.31	1.24	936.86
	base	1.31	5.19	3935.19
	subbase	4.53	17.96	13607.96
Station: 3+028.394				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	0.00	0.00	680892.54
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	478.04	11081.36	1367208.36
	topeka	0.31	7.46	925.55
	binder	0.31	7.61	944.47
	base	1.30	31.92	3967.12
	subbase	4.47	109.94	13717.91
Station: 3+044.680				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	0.00	0.00	680892.54
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	511.23	8055.53	1375263.89
	topeka	0.31	4.97	930.52
	binder	0.31	5.07	949.54
	base	1.30	21.20	3988.32
	subbase	4.44	72.56	13790.47
Station: 3+050.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	0.00	0.00	680892.54
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	521.97	2748.45	1378012.33
	topeka	0.31	1.62	932.15
	binder	0.31	1.65	951.19
	base	1.30	6.91	3995.23
	subbase	4.43	23.60	13814.07
Station: 3+060.965				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	0.00	0.00	680892.54
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	543.42	5841.24	1383853.58
	topeka	0.31	3.35	935.50
	binder	0.31	3.41	954.60
	base	1.30	14.23	4009.46
	subbase	4.41	48.49	13862.56
Station: 3+082.682				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	0.00	0.00	680892.54
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	583.77	12239.09	1396092.67
	topeka	0.31	6.63	942.12
	binder	0.31	6.74	961.34
	base	1.29	28.13	4037.59
	subbase	4.38	95.52	13958.07
Station: 3+085.394				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	0.00	0.00	680892.54
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	588.60	1589.95	1397682.62
	topeka	0.31	0.83	942.95
	binder	0.31	0.84	962.19

	base	1.29	3.51	4041.10
	subbase	4.38	11.88	13969.96
Station: 3+100.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	0.00	0.00	680892.54
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	615.76	8760.87	1406443.49
	topeka	0.31	4.46	947.41
	binder	0.31	4.53	966.72
	base	1.30	18.91	4060.01
	subbase	4.41	64.14	14034.10
Station: 3+101.680				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	0.00	0.00	680892.54
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	619.34	1037.33	1407480.82
	topeka	0.31	0.51	947.92
	binder	0.31	0.52	967.24
	base	1.30	2.18	4062.19
	subbase	4.41	7.41	14041.51
Station: 3+121.281				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	0.00	0.00	680892.54
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	650.00	12401.48	1419882.31
	topeka	0.31	5.98	953.90
	binder	0.31	6.09	973.33
	base	1.30	25.41	4087.60
	subbase	4.41	86.41	14127.92
Station: 3+125.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	0.00	0.00	680892.54
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	649.09	2415.67	1422297.97
	topeka	0.31	1.14	955.04
	binder	0.31	1.16	974.49
	base	1.30	4.82	4092.43
	subbase	4.41	16.41	14144.33
Station: 3+140.882				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	0.00	0.00	680892.54
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	620.79	10069.03	1432367.00
	topeka	0.31	4.85	959.88
	binder	0.31	4.93	979.42
	base	1.30	20.59	4113.02
	subbase	4.41	70.02	14214.34
Station: 3+150.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	0.00	0.00	680892.54
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	598.04	5556.51	1437923.51
	topeka	0.31	2.78	962.67
	binder	0.31	2.83	982.25
	base	1.29	11.81	4124.83
	subbase	4.39	40.13	14254.48

Station: 3+157.168				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	0.00	0.00	680892.54
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	576.77	4210.47	1442133.99
	topeka	0.31	2.19	964.85
	binder	0.31	2.22	984.47
	base	1.29	9.28	4134.11
	subbase	4.38	31.44	14285.92
Station: 3+159.880				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	0.00	0.00	680892.54
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	567.75	1552.19	1443686.18
	topeka	0.31	0.83	965.68
	binder	0.31	0.84	985.32
	base	1.29	3.51	4137.62
	subbase	4.38	11.88	14297.80
Station: 3+181.596				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	0.00	0.00	680892.54
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	494.57	11534.70	1455220.88
	topeka	0.31	6.63	972.31
	binder	0.31	6.74	992.06
	base	1.30	28.13	4165.75
	subbase	4.41	95.52	14393.32
Station: 3+197.882				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	0.00	0.00	680892.54
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	439.58	7606.59	1462827.48
	topeka	0.31	4.97	977.28
	binder	0.31	5.06	997.12
	base	1.30	21.15	4186.89
	subbase	4.44	72.09	14465.41
Station: 3+200.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	0.00	0.00	680892.54
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	432.40	923.34	1463750.81
	topeka	0.31	0.65	977.93
	binder	0.31	0.66	997.78
	base	1.30	2.75	4189.65
	subbase	4.44	9.41	14474.81
Station: 3+214.168				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	0.00	0.00	680892.54
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	384.80	5789.03	1469539.85
	topeka	0.31	4.33	982.25
	binder	0.31	4.41	1002.19
	base	1.30	18.45	4208.09
	subbase	4.47	63.15	14537.97
Station: 3+238.596				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	0.00	0.00	680892.54

	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	310.89	8497.41	1478037.25
	topeka	0.31	7.46	989.72
	binder	0.31	7.61	1009.80
	base	1.31	31.92	4240.02
	subbase	4.53	109.94	14647.91
Station: 3+250.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	0.00	0.00	680892.54
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	280.62	3372.64	1481409.90
	topeka	0.31	3.49	993.20
	binder	0.31	3.56	1013.36
	base	1.31	14.94	4254.95
	subbase	4.53	51.66	14699.57
Station: 3+300.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	0.00	0.02	680892.56
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	174.02	11365.90	1492775.80
	topeka	0.31	15.28	1008.48
	binder	0.31	15.59	1028.95
	base	1.31	65.50	4320.45
	subbase	4.53	226.50	14926.07
Station: 3+350.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	0.00	0.00	680892.56
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	184.76	8969.35	1501745.14
	topeka	0.31	15.28	1023.76
	binder	0.31	15.59	1044.54
	base	1.31	65.50	4385.95
	subbase	4.53	226.50	15152.57
Station: 3+400.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	0.00	0.00	680892.56
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	188.44	9329.85	1511074.99
	topeka	0.31	15.28	1039.05
	binder	0.31	15.59	1060.14
	base	1.31	65.50	4451.45
	subbase	4.53	226.50	15379.07
Station: 3+450.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	0.00	0.00	680892.56
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	184.03	9311.77	1520386.76
	topeka	0.31	15.28	1054.33
	binder	0.31	15.59	1075.73
	base	1.31	65.50	4516.95
	subbase	4.53	226.50	15605.57
Station: 3+500.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	0.00	0.00	680892.56
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	91.19	6880.71	1527267.47
	topeka	0.31	15.28	1069.61

	binder	0.31	15.59	1091.32
	base	1.31	65.50	4582.45
	subbase	4.53	226.50	15832.07
Station: 3+550.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	2.36	58.96	680951.52
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	6.11	2432.72	1529700.19
	topeka	0.31	15.28	1084.89
	binder	0.31	15.59	1106.92
	base	1.31	65.50	4647.95
	subbase	4.53	226.50	16058.57
Station: 3+600.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	28.58	773.48	681725.01
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.00	152.85	1529853.04
	topeka	0.31	15.28	1100.17
	binder	0.31	15.59	1122.51
	base	1.31	65.50	4713.45
	subbase	4.53	226.50	16285.07
Station: 3+650.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	43.27	1796.34	683521.35
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.26	6.60	1529859.64
	topeka	0.31	15.28	1115.45
	binder	0.31	15.59	1138.11
	base	1.31	65.50	4778.95
	subbase	4.53	226.50	16511.57
Station: 3+700.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	64.96	2705.78	686227.13
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.00	6.60	1529866.25
	topeka	0.31	15.28	1130.73
	binder	0.31	15.59	1153.70
	base	1.31	65.50	4844.45
	subbase	4.53	226.50	16738.07
Station: 3+750.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	46.67	2790.68	689017.81
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.00	0.00	1529866.25
	topeka	0.31	15.28	1146.01
	binder	0.31	15.59	1169.29
	base	1.31	65.50	4909.95
	subbase	4.53	226.50	16964.57
Station: 3+800.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	22.97	1740.96	690758.77
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.00	0.00	1529866.25
	topeka	0.31	15.28	1161.30
	binder	0.31	15.59	1184.89
	base	1.31	65.50	4975.45

	subbase	4.53	226.50	17191.07
Station: 3+850.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	6.60	739.12	691497.89
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.00	0.00	1529866.25
	topeka	0.31	15.28	1176.58
	binder	0.31	15.59	1200.48
	base	1.31	65.50	5040.95
	subbase	4.53	226.50	17417.57
Station: 3+900.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	1.40	199.84	691697.73
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.06	1.49	1529867.74
	topeka	0.31	15.28	1191.86
	binder	0.31	15.59	1216.07
	base	1.31	65.50	5106.45
	subbase	4.53	226.50	17644.07
Station: 3+950.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	0.00	34.97	691732.70
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	3.50	89.05	1529956.79
	topeka	0.31	15.28	1207.14
	binder	0.31	15.59	1231.67
	base	1.31	65.50	5171.95
	subbase	4.53	226.50	17870.57
Station: 4+000.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	0.00	0.01	691732.71
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	18.88	559.63	1530516.42
	topeka	0.31	15.28	1222.42
	binder	0.31	15.59	1247.26
	base	1.31	65.50	5237.45
	subbase	4.53	226.50	18097.07
Station: 4+050.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	0.00	0.22	691732.93
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	28.38	1181.62	1531698.04
	topeka	0.31	15.28	1237.70
	binder	0.31	15.59	1262.86
	base	1.31	65.50	5302.95
	subbase	4.53	226.50	18323.57
Station: 4+100.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	0.00	0.22	691733.15
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	70.93	2482.81	1534180.84
	topeka	0.31	15.28	1252.98
	binder	0.31	15.59	1278.45
	base	1.31	65.50	5368.45
	subbase	4.53	226.50	18550.07
Station: 4+150.000				

	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	0.00	0.00	691733.15
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	102.13	4326.50	1538507.34
	topeka	0.31	15.28	1268.26
	binder	0.31	15.59	1294.04
	base	1.31	65.50	5433.95
	subbase	4.53	226.50	18776.57
Station: 4+200.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	0.00	0.00	691733.15
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	150.69	6320.40	1544827.75
	topeka	0.31	15.28	1283.55
	binder	0.31	15.59	1309.64
	base	1.31	65.50	5499.45
	subbase	4.53	226.50	19003.07
Station: 4+250.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	0.00	0.00	691733.15
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	206.53	8930.33	1553758.08
	topeka	0.31	15.28	1298.83
	binder	0.31	15.59	1325.23
	base	1.31	65.50	5564.95
	subbase	4.53	226.50	19229.57
Station: 4+300.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	0.00	0.00	691733.15
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	269.25	11894.39	1565652.47
	topeka	0.31	15.28	1314.11
	binder	0.31	15.59	1340.82
	base	1.31	65.50	5630.45
	subbase	4.53	226.50	19456.07
Station: 4+350.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	0.00	0.00	691733.15
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	337.79	15176.01	1580828.48
	topeka	0.31	15.28	1329.39
	binder	0.31	15.59	1356.42
	base	1.31	65.50	5695.95
	subbase	4.53	226.50	19682.57
Station: 4+400.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	0.00	0.00	691733.15
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	411.96	18743.80	1599572.28
	topeka	0.31	15.28	1344.67
	binder	0.31	15.59	1372.01
	base	1.31	65.50	5761.45
	subbase	4.53	226.50	19909.07
Station: 4+450.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	0.00	0.00	691733.15
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	473.66	22140.41	1621712.69

	topeka	0.31	15.28	1359.95
	binder	0.31	15.59	1387.61
	base	1.31	65.50	5826.95
	subbase	4.53	226.50	20135.57
Station: 4+500.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	0.00	0.00	691733.15
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	492.64	24157.39	1645870.08
	topeka	0.31	15.28	1375.23
	binder	0.31	15.59	1403.20
	base	1.31	65.50	5892.45
	subbase	4.53	226.50	20362.07
Station: 4+550.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	0.00	0.00	691733.15
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	479.17	24295.24	1670165.32
	topeka	0.31	15.28	1390.51
	binder	0.31	15.59	1418.79
	base	1.31	65.50	5957.95
	subbase	4.53	226.50	20588.57
Station: 4+600.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	0.00	0.00	691733.15
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	435.02	22854.74	1693020.06
	topeka	0.31	15.28	1405.80
	binder	0.31	15.59	1434.39
	base	1.31	65.50	6023.45
	subbase	4.53	226.50	20815.07
Station: 4+650.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	0.00	0.00	691733.15
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	318.28	18832.52	1711852.58
	topeka	0.31	15.28	1421.08
	binder	0.31	15.59	1449.98
	base	1.31	65.50	6088.95
	subbase	4.53	226.50	21041.57
Station: 4+700.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	0.00	0.00	691733.15
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	233.94	13805.63	1725658.21
	topeka	0.31	15.28	1436.36
	binder	0.31	15.59	1465.57
	base	1.31	65.50	6154.45
	subbase	4.53	226.50	21268.07
Station: 4+750.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	0.01	0.37	691733.52
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	179.49	10335.97	1735994.17
	topeka	0.31	15.28	1451.64
	binder	0.31	15.59	1481.17

	base	1.31	65.50	6219.95
	subbase	4.53	226.50	21494.57
Station: 4+800.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	0.00	0.37	691733.89
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	214.17	9841.54	1745835.71
	topeka	0.31	15.28	1466.92
	binder	0.31	15.59	1496.76
	base	1.31	65.50	6285.45
	subbase	4.53	226.50	21721.07
Station: 4+850.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	0.00	0.00	691733.89
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	183.83	9949.86	1755785.57
	topeka	0.31	15.28	1482.20
	binder	0.31	15.59	1512.36
	base	1.31	65.50	6350.95
	subbase	4.53	226.50	21947.57
Station: 4+900.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	0.00	0.00	691733.89
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	136.71	8013.36	1763798.94
	topeka	0.31	15.28	1497.48
	binder	0.31	15.59	1527.95
	base	1.31	65.50	6416.45
	subbase	4.53	226.50	22174.07
Station: 4+950.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	0.00	0.00	691733.90
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	123.78	6512.21	1770311.14
	topeka	0.31	15.28	1512.76
	binder	0.31	15.59	1543.54
	base	1.31	65.50	6481.95
	subbase	4.53	226.50	22400.57
Station: 5+000.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	0.00	0.00	691733.90
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	143.36	6678.66	1776989.80
	topeka	0.31	15.28	1528.05
	binder	0.31	15.59	1559.14
	base	1.31	65.50	6547.45
	subbase	4.53	226.50	22627.07
Station: 5+050.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	0.00	0.00	691733.90
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	147.31	7266.82	1784256.63
	topeka	0.31	15.28	1543.33
	binder	0.31	15.59	1574.73
	base	1.31	65.50	6612.95
	subbase	4.53	226.50	22853.57

Station: 5+100.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	0.00	0.00	691733.90
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	115.14	6561.08	1790817.71
	topeka	0.31	15.28	1558.61
	binder	0.31	15.59	1590.32
	base	1.31	65.50	6678.45
	subbase	4.53	226.50	23080.07
Station: 5+118.534				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	0.00	0.00	691733.90
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	85.02	1854.87	1792672.58
	topeka	0.31	5.66	1564.27
	binder	0.31	5.78	1596.10
	base	1.31	24.28	6702.73
	subbase	4.53	83.96	23164.03
Station: 5+142.962				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	0.00	0.00	691733.90
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	51.54	1668.09	1794340.67
	topeka	0.31	7.46	1571.74
	binder	0.31	7.61	1603.72
	base	1.30	31.92	6734.66
	subbase	4.47	109.94	23273.97
Station: 5+150.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	0.00	0.00	691733.90
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	43.57	334.69	1794675.36
	topeka	0.31	2.15	1573.89
	binder	0.31	2.19	1605.91
	base	1.30	9.17	6743.82
	subbase	4.46	31.42	23305.39
Station: 5+159.248				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	0.00	0.00	691733.90
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	29.33	337.08	1795012.44
	topeka	0.31	2.82	1576.71
	binder	0.31	2.88	1608.78
	base	1.30	12.03	6755.85
	subbase	4.44	41.14	23346.53
Station: 5+175.534				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	9.24	75.25	691809.15
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.18	240.25	1795252.69
	topeka	0.31	4.97	1581.68
	binder	0.31	5.06	1613.84
	base	1.30	21.15	6777.00
	subbase	4.41	72.09	23418.62
Station: 5+197.250				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	30.29	429.27	692238.42

	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.00	1.94	1795254.62
	topeka	0.31	6.63	1588.31
	binder	0.31	6.74	1620.59
	base	1.29	28.13	6805.13
	subbase	4.38	95.52	23514.14
Station: 5+199.962				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	30.33	82.22	692320.64
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.00	0.00	1795254.62
	topeka	0.31	0.83	1589.14
	binder	0.31	0.84	1621.43
	base	1.29	3.51	6808.64
	subbase	4.38	11.88	23526.02
Station: 5+200.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	30.34	1.14	692321.78
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.00	0.00	1795254.62
	topeka	0.31	0.01	1589.15
	binder	0.31	0.01	1621.44
	base	1.29	0.05	6808.69
	subbase	4.38	0.16	23526.19
Station: 5+216.248				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	34.37	524.96	692846.73
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.00	0.00	1795254.62
	topeka	0.31	4.96	1594.10
	binder	0.31	5.04	1626.48
	base	1.30	21.04	6829.73
	subbase	4.41	71.38	23597.57
Station: 5+225.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	38.19	317.49	693164.22
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.00	0.00	1795254.62
	topeka	0.31	2.67	1596.78
	binder	0.31	2.72	1629.20
	base	1.30	11.35	6841.08
	subbase	4.41	38.61	23636.18
Station: 5+250.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	51.06	1112.14	694276.36
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.00	0.10	1795254.72
	topeka	0.31	7.63	1604.41
	binder	0.31	7.77	1636.97
	base	1.30	32.41	6873.49
	subbase	4.41	110.21	23746.39
Station: 5+275.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	71.31	1526.95	695803.31
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.00	0.10	1795254.81
	topeka	0.31	7.63	1612.04

	binder	0.31	7.77	1644.73
	base	1.30	32.41	6905.90
	subbase	4.41	110.21	23856.61
Station: 5+300.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	86.84	1972.74	697776.05
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.00	0.00	1795254.81
	topeka	0.31	7.63	1619.67
	binder	0.31	7.77	1652.50
	base	1.30	32.41	6938.32
	subbase	4.41	110.21	23966.82
Station: 5+325.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	110.72	2462.48	700238.53
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.00	0.00	1795254.81
	topeka	0.31	7.63	1627.30
	binder	0.31	7.77	1660.26
	base	1.30	32.41	6970.73
	subbase	4.41	110.21	24077.03
Station: 5+350.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	136.35	3079.93	703318.46
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.02	0.27	1795255.08
	topeka	0.31	7.63	1634.93
	binder	0.31	7.77	1668.03
	base	1.30	32.41	7003.15
	subbase	4.41	110.21	24187.25
Station: 5+359.753				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	149.15	1392.26	704710.72
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.00	0.10	1795255.19
	topeka	0.31	2.98	1637.90
	binder	0.31	3.03	1671.06
	base	1.30	12.65	7015.79
	subbase	4.41	43.02	24230.27
Station: 5+375.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	161.84	2366.45	707077.17
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.00	0.00	1795255.19
	topeka	0.31	4.65	1642.56
	binder	0.31	4.74	1675.80
	base	1.30	19.77	7035.56
	subbase	4.41	67.22	24297.49
Station: 5+400.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	176.25	4219.41	711296.58
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.00	0.00	1795255.19
	topeka	0.31	7.63	1650.19
	binder	0.31	7.77	1683.56
	base	1.30	32.41	7067.98

	subbase	4.41	110.21	24407.70
Station: 5+425.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	178.41	4427.61	715724.19
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.00	0.00	1795255.19
	topeka	0.31	7.63	1657.82
	binder	0.31	7.77	1691.33
	base	1.30	32.41	7100.39
	subbase	4.41	110.21	24517.91
Station: 5+450.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	192.14	4631.19	720355.38
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.26	3.37	1795258.56
	topeka	0.31	7.63	1665.45
	binder	0.31	7.77	1699.09
	base	1.30	32.41	7132.80
	subbase	4.41	110.21	24628.12
Station: 5+475.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	343.08	6733.90	727089.27
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.00	3.41	1795261.97
	topeka	0.31	7.63	1673.08
	binder	0.31	7.77	1706.86
	base	1.30	32.41	7165.22
	subbase	4.41	110.21	24738.34
Station: 5+500.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	347.43	8724.01	735813.28
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.00	0.05	1795262.02
	topeka	0.31	7.63	1680.71
	binder	0.31	7.77	1714.62
	base	1.30	32.41	7197.63
	subbase	4.41	110.21	24848.55
Station: 5+503.258				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	357.61	1148.59	736961.87
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.00	0.00	1795262.02
	topeka	0.31	0.99	1681.70
	binder	0.31	1.01	1715.63
	base	1.30	4.23	7201.85
	subbase	4.41	14.37	24862.92
Station: 5+519.544				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	498.74	7043.74	744005.62
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.00	0.00	1795262.02
	topeka	0.31	4.97	1686.67
	binder	0.31	5.06	1720.69
	base	1.29	21.09	7222.94
	subbase	4.38	71.55	24934.47
Station: 5+522.256				

	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	525.51	1389.08	745394.69
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.00	0.00	1795262.02
	topeka	0.31	0.83	1687.50
	binder	0.31	0.84	1721.53
	base	1.29	3.51	7226.45
	subbase	4.38	11.88	24946.36
Station: 5+543.973				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	757.88	13935.15	759329.85
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.00	0.00	1795262.02
	topeka	0.31	6.63	1694.13
	binder	0.31	6.74	1728.27
	base	1.30	28.13	7254.58
	subbase	4.41	95.52	25041.87
Station: 5+550.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	825.89	4773.06	764102.91
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.00	0.00	1795262.02
	topeka	0.31	1.84	1695.97
	binder	0.31	1.87	1730.15
	base	1.30	7.82	7262.40
	subbase	4.42	26.63	25068.50
Station: 5+560.258				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	943.36	9074.66	773177.57
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.00	0.00	1795262.02
	topeka	0.31	3.13	1699.10
	binder	0.31	3.19	1733.34
	base	1.30	13.33	7275.73
	subbase	4.44	45.46	25113.96
Station: 5+576.544				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	1117.19	16778.73	789956.29
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.00	0.00	1795262.02
	topeka	0.31	4.97	1704.07
	binder	0.31	5.07	1738.40
	base	1.30	21.20	7296.93
	subbase	4.47	72.56	25186.52
Station: 5+600.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	1309.07	28455.20	818411.49
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.00	0.00	1795262.02
	topeka	0.31	7.17	1711.24
	binder	0.31	7.31	1745.71
	base	1.31	30.65	7327.58
	subbase	4.53	105.54	25292.06
Station: 5+600.973				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	1315.44	1276.20	819687.70
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.00	0.00	1795262.02

	topeka	0.31	0.30	1711.53
	binder	0.31	0.30	1746.01
	base	1.31	1.27	7328.85
	subbase	4.53	4.40	25296.46
Station: 5+650.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	1381.78	66118.95	885806.65
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.00	0.00	1795262.02
	topeka	0.31	14.98	1726.52
	binder	0.31	15.29	1761.30
	base	1.31	64.23	7393.08
	subbase	4.53	222.09	25518.56
Station: 5+700.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	1354.90	68416.96	954223.61
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.00	0.00	1795262.02
	topeka	0.31	15.28	1741.80
	binder	0.31	15.59	1776.90
	base	1.31	65.50	7458.58
	subbase	4.53	226.50	25745.06
Station: 5+750.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	1360.90	67894.96	1022118.56
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.00	0.00	1795262.02
	topeka	0.31	15.28	1757.08
	binder	0.31	15.59	1792.49
	base	1.31	65.50	7524.08
	subbase	4.53	226.50	25971.56
Station: 5+800.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	1374.75	68391.14	1090509.70
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.00	0.00	1795262.02
	topeka	0.31	15.28	1772.36
	binder	0.31	15.59	1808.09
	base	1.31	65.50	7589.58
	subbase	4.53	226.50	26198.06
Station: 5+850.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	1364.17	68472.89	1158982.59
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.00	0.00	1795262.02
	topeka	0.31	15.28	1787.64
	binder	0.31	15.59	1823.68
	base	1.31	65.50	7655.08
	subbase	4.53	226.50	26424.56
Station: 5+900.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	1305.01	66729.38	1225711.97
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.00	0.00	1795262.02
	topeka	0.31	15.28	1802.92
	binder	0.31	15.59	1839.27

	base	1.31	65.50	7720.58
	subbase	4.53	226.50	26651.06
Station: 5+950.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	1241.03	63650.93	1289362.89
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.00	0.00	1795262.02
	topeka	0.31	15.28	1818.21
	binder	0.31	15.59	1854.87
	base	1.31	65.50	7786.08
	subbase	4.53	226.50	26877.56
Station: 6+000.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	1204.13	61129.08	1350491.97
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.00	0.00	1795262.02
	topeka	0.31	15.28	1833.49
	binder	0.31	15.59	1870.46
	base	1.31	65.50	7851.58
	subbase	4.53	226.50	27104.06
Station: 6+050.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	1180.00	59603.28	1410095.25
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.00	0.00	1795262.02
	topeka	0.31	15.28	1848.77
	binder	0.31	15.59	1886.05
	base	1.31	65.50	7917.08
	subbase	4.53	226.50	27330.56
Station: 6+100.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	1105.96	57148.87	1467244.12
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.00	0.00	1795262.02
	topeka	0.31	15.28	1864.05
	binder	0.31	15.59	1901.65
	base	1.31	65.50	7982.58
	subbase	4.53	226.50	27557.06
Station: 6+150.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	971.86	51945.35	1519189.48
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.00	0.00	1795262.02
	topeka	0.31	15.28	1879.33
	binder	0.31	15.59	1917.24
	base	1.31	65.50	8048.08
	subbase	4.53	226.50	27783.56
Station: 6+200.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	831.55	45085.09	1564274.57
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.00	0.00	1795262.02
	topeka	0.31	15.28	1894.61
	binder	0.31	15.59	1932.84
	base	1.31	65.50	8113.58
	subbase	4.53	226.50	28010.06

Station: 6+250.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	689.28	38020.57	1602295.14
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.00	0.00	1795262.02
	topeka	0.31	15.28	1909.89
	binder	0.31	15.59	1948.43
	base	1.31	65.50	8179.08
	subbase	4.53	226.50	28236.56
Station: 6+300.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	547.17	30911.14	1633206.28
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.00	0.00	1795262.02
	topeka	0.31	15.28	1925.17
	binder	0.31	15.59	1964.02
	base	1.31	65.50	8244.58
	subbase	4.53	226.50	28463.06
Station: 6+350.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	411.26	23960.85	1657167.13
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.00	0.00	1795262.02
	topeka	0.31	15.28	1940.46
	binder	0.31	15.59	1979.62
	base	1.31	65.50	8310.08
	subbase	4.53	226.50	28689.56
Station: 6+400.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	284.83	17402.25	1674569.38
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.00	0.00	1795262.02
	topeka	0.31	15.28	1955.74
	binder	0.31	15.59	1995.21
	base	1.31	65.50	8375.58
	subbase	4.53	226.50	28916.06
Station: 6+450.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	170.26	11377.23	1685946.61
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.00	0.00	1795262.02
	topeka	0.31	15.28	1971.02
	binder	0.31	15.59	2010.80
	base	1.31	65.50	8441.08
	subbase	4.53	226.50	29142.56
Station: 6+500.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	120.73	7274.85	1693221.46
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.00	0.00	1795262.02
	topeka	0.31	15.28	1986.30
	binder	0.31	15.59	2026.40
	base	1.31	65.50	8506.58
	subbase	4.53	226.50	29369.06
Station: 6+550.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	105.88	5665.31	1698886.77

	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.00	0.02	1795262.03
	topeka	0.31	15.28	2001.58
	binder	0.31	15.59	2041.99
	base	1.31	65.50	8572.08
	subbase	4.53	226.50	29595.56
Station: 6+600.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	105.50	5284.53	1704171.29
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.00	0.02	1795262.05
	topeka	0.31	15.28	2016.86
	binder	0.31	15.59	2057.59
	base	1.31	65.50	8637.58
	subbase	4.53	226.50	29822.06
Station: 6+650.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	103.90	5235.03	1709406.33
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.00	0.00	1795262.05
	topeka	0.31	15.28	2032.14
	binder	0.31	15.59	2073.18
	base	1.31	65.50	8703.08
	subbase	4.53	226.50	30048.56
Station: 6+700.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	95.63	4988.24	1714394.57
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.00	0.00	1795262.05
	topeka	0.31	15.28	2047.42
	binder	0.31	15.59	2088.77
	base	1.31	65.50	8768.58
	subbase	4.53	226.50	30275.06
Station: 6+750.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	91.61	4680.89	1719075.46
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.00	0.00	1795262.06
	topeka	0.31	15.28	2062.71
	binder	0.31	15.59	2104.37
	base	1.31	65.50	8834.08
	subbase	4.53	226.50	30501.56
Station: 6+800.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	97.61	4730.52	1723805.98
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.00	0.00	1795262.07
	topeka	0.31	15.28	2077.99
	binder	0.31	15.59	2119.96
	base	1.31	65.50	8899.58
	subbase	4.53	226.50	30728.06
Station: 6+850.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	94.84	4811.36	1728617.33
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.00	0.00	1795262.07
	topeka	0.31	15.28	2093.27

	binder	0.31	15.59	2135.55
	base	1.31	65.50	8965.08
	subbase	4.53	226.50	30954.56
Station: 6+900.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	95.93	4769.24	1733386.58
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.00	0.00	1795262.07
	topeka	0.31	15.28	2108.55
	binder	0.31	15.59	2151.15
	base	1.31	65.50	9030.58
	subbase	4.53	226.50	31181.06
Station: 6+950.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	99.36	4882.19	1738268.76
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.00	0.00	1795262.07
	topeka	0.31	15.28	2123.83
	binder	0.31	15.59	2166.74
	base	1.31	65.50	9096.08
	subbase	4.53	226.50	31407.56
Station: 7+000.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	106.98	5158.58	1743427.34
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.00	0.00	1795262.07
	topeka	0.31	15.28	2139.11
	binder	0.31	15.59	2182.34
	base	1.31	65.50	9161.58
	subbase	4.53	226.50	31634.06
Station: 7+050.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	107.85	5370.77	1748798.11
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.00	0.00	1795262.07
	topeka	0.31	15.28	2154.39
	binder	0.31	15.59	2197.93
	base	1.31	65.50	9227.08
	subbase	4.53	226.50	31860.56
Station: 7+100.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	87.94	4894.69	1753692.80
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.00	0.00	1795262.07
	topeka	0.31	15.28	2169.67
	binder	0.31	15.59	2213.52
	base	1.31	65.50	9292.58
	subbase	4.53	226.50	32087.06
Station: 7+150.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	75.79	4093.20	1757786.00
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.00	0.00	1795262.07
	topeka	0.31	15.28	2184.96
	binder	0.31	15.59	2229.12
	base	1.31	65.50	9358.08

	subbase	4.53	226.50	32313.56
Station: 7+200.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	67.55	3583.48	1761369.49
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.00	0.00	1795262.07
	topeka	0.31	15.28	2200.24
	binder	0.31	15.59	2244.71
	base	1.31	65.50	9423.58
	subbase	4.53	226.50	32540.06
Station: 7+250.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	74.57	3553.13	1764922.62
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.00	0.00	1795262.07
	topeka	0.31	15.28	2215.52
	binder	0.31	15.59	2260.30
	base	1.31	65.50	9489.08
	subbase	4.53	226.50	32766.56
Station: 7+300.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	84.78	3983.86	1768906.48
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.00	0.00	1795262.07
	topeka	0.31	15.28	2230.80
	binder	0.31	15.59	2275.90
	base	1.31	65.50	9554.58
	subbase	4.53	226.50	32993.06
Station: 7+350.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	97.66	4561.18	1773467.67
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.00	0.00	1795262.07
	topeka	0.31	15.28	2246.08
	binder	0.31	15.59	2291.49
	base	1.31	65.50	9620.08
	subbase	4.53	226.50	33219.56
Station: 7+400.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	95.44	4827.70	1778295.37
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.00	0.00	1795262.07
	topeka	0.31	15.28	2261.36
	binder	0.31	15.59	2307.09
	base	1.31	65.50	9685.58
	subbase	4.53	226.50	33446.06
Station: 7+450.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	98.71	4853.95	1783149.31
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.00	0.00	1795262.07
	topeka	0.31	15.28	2276.64
	binder	0.31	15.59	2322.68
	base	1.31	65.50	9751.08
	subbase	4.53	226.50	33672.56
Station: 7+500.000				

	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	102.03	5018.51	1788167.83
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.00	0.00	1795262.07
	topeka	0.31	15.28	2291.92
	binder	0.31	15.59	2338.27
	base	1.31	65.50	9816.58
	subbase	4.53	226.50	33899.06
Station: 7+550.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	104.19	5155.48	1793323.30
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.00	0.00	1795262.07
	topeka	0.31	15.28	2307.21
	binder	0.31	15.59	2353.87
	base	1.31	65.50	9882.08
	subbase	4.53	226.50	34125.56
Station: 7+600.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	97.91	5052.45	1798375.76
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.00	0.00	1795262.08
	topeka	0.31	15.28	2322.49
	binder	0.31	15.59	2369.46
	base	1.31	65.50	9947.58
	subbase	4.53	226.50	34352.06
Station: 7+650.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	66.95	4121.39	1802497.15
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.00	0.00	1795262.08
	topeka	0.31	15.28	2337.77
	binder	0.31	15.59	2385.05
	base	1.31	65.50	10013.08
	subbase	4.53	226.50	34578.56
Station: 7+700.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	36.90	2596.18	1805093.33
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.00	0.00	1795262.08
	topeka	0.31	15.28	2353.05
	binder	0.31	15.59	2400.65
	base	1.31	65.50	10078.58
	subbase	4.53	226.50	34805.06
Station: 7+750.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	19.46	1408.92	1806502.25
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.00	0.00	1795262.08
	topeka	0.31	15.28	2368.33
	binder	0.31	15.59	2416.24
	base	1.31	65.50	10144.08
	subbase	4.53	226.50	35031.56
Station: 7+800.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	10.67	753.28	1807255.54
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.00	0.00	1795262.08

	topeka	0.31	15.28	2383.61
	binder	0.31	15.59	2431.84
	base	1.31	65.50	10209.58
	subbase	4.53	226.50	35258.06
Station: 7+850.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	7.19	446.44	1807701.98
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.00	0.00	1795262.08
	topeka	0.31	15.28	2398.89
	binder	0.31	15.59	2447.43
	base	1.31	65.50	10275.08
	subbase	4.53	226.50	35484.56
Station: 7+900.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	2.85	250.99	1807952.97
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.00	0.00	1795262.08
	topeka	0.31	15.28	2414.17
	binder	0.31	15.59	2463.02
	base	1.31	65.50	10340.58
	subbase	4.53	226.50	35711.06
Station: 7+942.447				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	1.53	93.06	1808046.02
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.15	3.27	1795265.35
	topeka	0.31	12.97	2427.15
	binder	0.31	13.24	2476.26
	base	1.31	55.61	10396.18
	subbase	4.53	192.29	35903.35
Station: 7+950.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	1.24	10.46	1808056.48
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.30	1.72	1795267.07
	topeka	0.31	2.31	2429.46
	binder	0.31	2.36	2478.62
	base	1.31	9.89	10406.08
	subbase	4.53	34.21	35937.56
Station: 8+000.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	0.10	33.37	1808089.85
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	2.08	59.47	1795326.55
	topeka	0.31	15.28	2444.74
	binder	0.31	15.59	2494.21
	base	1.31	65.50	10471.58
	subbase	4.53	226.50	36164.06
Station: 8+050.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	0.06	3.88	1808093.73
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	3.34	135.44	1795461.98
	topeka	0.31	15.28	2460.02
	binder	0.31	15.59	2509.80

	base	1.31	65.50	10537.08
	subbase	4.53	226.50	36390.56
Station: 8+100.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	3.52	89.54	1808183.28
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.28	90.62	1795552.60
	topeka	0.31	15.28	2475.30
	binder	0.31	15.59	2525.40
	base	1.31	65.50	10602.58
	subbase	4.53	226.50	36617.06
Station: 8+150.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	28.56	801.97	1808985.24
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.00	7.09	1795559.69
	topeka	0.31	15.28	2490.58
	binder	0.31	15.59	2540.99
	base	1.31	65.50	10668.08
	subbase	4.53	226.50	36843.56
Station: 8+200.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	55.23	2094.64	1811079.89
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.00	0.00	1795559.69
	topeka	0.31	15.28	2505.86
	binder	0.31	15.59	2556.59
	base	1.31	65.50	10733.58
	subbase	4.53	226.50	37070.06
Station: 8+250.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	90.10	3633.28	1814713.17
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.00	0.00	1795559.69
	topeka	0.31	15.28	2521.14
	binder	0.31	15.59	2572.18
	base	1.31	65.50	10799.08
	subbase	4.53	226.50	37296.56
Station: 8+300.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	116.56	5166.59	1819879.76
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.00	0.00	1795559.69
	topeka	0.31	15.28	2536.42
	binder	0.31	15.59	2587.77
	base	1.31	65.50	10864.58
	subbase	4.53	226.50	37523.06
Station: 8+350.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	131.24	6195.03	1826074.78
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.00	0.00	1795559.69
	topeka	0.31	15.28	2551.71
	binder	0.31	15.59	2603.37
	base	1.31	65.50	10930.08
	subbase	4.53	226.50	37749.56

Station: 8+400.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	100.08	5783.00	1831857.78
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.00	0.00	1795559.69
	topeka	0.31	15.28	2566.99
	binder	0.31	15.59	2618.96
	base	1.31	65.50	10995.58
	subbase	4.53	226.50	37976.06
Station: 8+450.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	74.50	4364.39	1836222.17
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.00	0.00	1795559.69
	topeka	0.31	15.28	2582.27
	binder	0.31	15.59	2634.55
	base	1.31	65.50	11061.08
	subbase	4.53	226.50	38202.56
Station: 8+500.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	45.86	3008.81	1839230.98
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.00	0.00	1795559.69
	topeka	0.31	15.28	2597.55
	binder	0.31	15.59	2650.15
	base	1.31	65.50	11126.58
	subbase	4.53	226.50	38429.06
Station: 8+550.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	19.54	1634.80	1840865.78
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.00	0.02	1795559.72
	topeka	0.31	15.28	2612.83
	binder	0.31	15.59	2665.74
	base	1.31	65.50	11192.08
	subbase	4.53	226.50	38655.56
Station: 8+600.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	21.36	1022.35	1841888.14
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.00	0.02	1795559.74
	topeka	0.31	15.28	2628.11
	binder	0.31	15.59	2681.34
	base	1.31	65.50	11257.58
	subbase	4.53	226.50	38882.06
Station: 8+650.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	40.00	1534.03	1843422.17
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.00	0.00	1795559.74
	topeka	0.31	15.28	2643.39
	binder	0.31	15.59	2696.93
	base	1.31	65.50	11323.08
	subbase	4.53	226.50	39108.56
Station: 8+700.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	51.18	2279.52	1845701.69

	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.00	0.00	1795559.74
	topeka	0.31	15.28	2658.67
	binder	0.31	15.59	2712.52
	base	1.31	65.50	11388.58
	subbase	4.53	226.50	39335.06
Station: 8+750.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	63.90	2876.96	1848578.65
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.00	0.00	1795559.74
	topeka	0.31	15.28	2673.96
	binder	0.31	15.59	2728.12
	base	1.31	65.50	11454.08
	subbase	4.53	226.50	39561.56
Station: 8+800.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	53.35	2931.37	1851510.02
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.00	0.00	1795559.74
	topeka	0.31	15.28	2689.24
	binder	0.31	15.59	2743.71
	base	1.31	65.50	11519.58
	subbase	4.53	226.50	39788.06
Station: 8+850.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	45.49	2471.14	1853981.15
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.00	0.00	1795559.74
	topeka	0.31	15.28	2704.52
	binder	0.31	15.59	2759.30
	base	1.31	65.50	11585.08
	subbase	4.53	226.50	40014.56
Station: 8+900.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	1.99	1187.01	1855168.16
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	1.74	43.45	1795603.19
	topeka	0.31	15.28	2719.80
	binder	0.31	15.59	2774.90
	base	1.31	65.50	11650.58
	subbase	4.53	226.50	40241.06
Station: 8+950.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	0.00	49.74	1855217.90
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	51.28	1325.39	1796928.58
	topeka	0.31	15.28	2735.08
	binder	0.31	15.59	2790.49
	base	1.31	65.50	11716.08
	subbase	4.53	226.50	40467.56
Station: 9+000.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	0.00	0.00	1855217.90
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	102.31	3839.78	1800768.36
	topeka	0.31	15.28	2750.36

	binder	0.31	15.59	2806.09
	base	1.31	65.50	11781.58
	subbase	4.53	226.50	40694.06
Station: 9+050.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	0.00	0.00	1855217.90
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	105.30	5190.42	1805958.78
	topeka	0.31	15.28	2765.64
	binder	0.31	15.59	2821.68
	base	1.31	65.50	11847.08
	subbase	4.53	226.50	40920.56
Station: 9+100.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	0.00	0.00	1855217.90
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	107.28	5314.62	1811273.41
	topeka	0.31	15.28	2780.92
	binder	0.31	15.59	2837.27
	base	1.31	65.50	11912.58
	subbase	4.53	226.50	41147.06
Station: 9+150.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	0.00	0.00	1855217.90
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	115.78	5576.54	1816849.94
	topeka	0.31	15.28	2796.21
	binder	0.31	15.59	2852.87
	base	1.31	65.50	11978.08
	subbase	4.53	226.50	41373.56
Station: 9+200.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	0.00	0.00	1855217.90
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	142.47	6456.29	1823306.23
	topeka	0.31	15.28	2811.49
	binder	0.31	15.59	2868.46
	base	1.31	65.50	12043.58
	subbase	4.53	226.50	41600.06
Station: 9+250.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	0.00	0.00	1855217.90
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	199.06	8538.18	1831844.41
	topeka	0.31	15.28	2826.77
	binder	0.31	15.59	2884.05
	base	1.31	65.50	12109.08
	subbase	4.53	226.50	41826.56
Station: 9+300.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	0.00	0.00	1855217.90
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	230.27	10733.24	1842577.65
	topeka	0.31	15.28	2842.05
	binder	0.31	15.59	2899.65
	base	1.31	65.50	12174.58

	subbase	4.53	226.50	42053.06
Station: 9+350.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	0.00	0.00	1855217.90
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	267.46	12443.40	1855021.05
	topeka	0.31	15.28	2857.33
	binder	0.31	15.59	2915.24
	base	1.31	65.50	12240.08
	subbase	4.53	226.50	42279.56
Station: 9+400.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	0.00	0.00	1855217.90
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	212.63	12002.42	1867023.47
	topeka	0.31	15.28	2872.61
	binder	0.31	15.59	2930.84
	base	1.31	65.50	12305.58
	subbase	4.53	226.50	42506.06
Station: 9+450.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	0.00	0.02	1855217.92
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	98.28	7772.98	1874796.45
	topeka	0.31	15.28	2887.89
	binder	0.31	15.59	2946.43
	base	1.31	65.50	12371.08
	subbase	4.53	226.50	42732.56
Station: 9+479.038				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	0.00	0.01	1855217.93
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	77.99	2559.31	1877355.76
	topeka	0.31	8.87	2896.77
	binder	0.31	9.06	2955.49
	base	1.31	38.04	12409.12
	subbase	4.53	131.54	42864.10
Station: 9+500.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	0.00	0.00	1855217.93
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	68.78	1538.27	1878894.03
	topeka	0.31	6.40	2903.17
	binder	0.31	6.53	2962.02
	base	1.30	27.40	12436.52
	subbase	4.48	94.42	42958.52
Station: 9+503.467				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	0.00	0.00	1855217.93
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	68.57	238.08	1879132.11
	topeka	0.31	1.06	2904.23
	binder	0.31	1.08	2963.10
	base	1.30	4.52	12441.04
	subbase	4.47	15.51	42974.04
Station: 9+519.753				

	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	0.00	0.00	1855217.93
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	67.58	1108.58	1880240.69
	topeka	0.31	4.97	2909.20
	binder	0.31	5.07	2968.16
	base	1.30	21.20	12462.24
	subbase	4.44	72.56	43046.60
Station: 9+536.038				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	0.00	0.00	1855217.93
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	84.94	1241.90	1881482.59
	topeka	0.31	4.97	2914.18
	binder	0.31	5.06	2973.22
	base	1.30	21.15	12483.38
	subbase	4.41	72.09	43118.69
Station: 9+550.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	0.00	0.03	1855217.96
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	98.11	1277.82	1882760.41
	topeka	0.31	4.26	2918.44
	binder	0.31	4.34	2977.56
	base	1.29	18.09	12501.48
	subbase	4.39	61.48	43180.17
Station: 9+557.754				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	0.00	0.02	1855217.98
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	107.58	797.49	1883557.91
	topeka	0.31	2.37	2920.80
	binder	0.31	2.41	2979.97
	base	1.29	10.04	12511.51
	subbase	4.38	34.03	43214.20
Station: 9+560.467				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	0.00	0.00	1855217.98
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	111.91	297.67	1883855.58
	topeka	0.31	0.83	2921.63
	binder	0.31	0.84	2980.81
	base	1.29	3.51	12515.02
	subbase	4.38	11.88	43226.08
Station: 9+575.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	0.00	0.00	1855217.98
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	141.00	1842.49	1885698.07
	topeka	0.31	4.43	2926.07
	binder	0.31	4.51	2985.32
	base	1.30	18.82	12533.84
	subbase	4.41	63.82	43289.90
Station: 9+576.753				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	0.00	0.00	1855217.98
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	144.73	250.38	1885948.44

	topeka	0.31	0.53	2926.60
	binder	0.31	0.54	2985.87
	base	1.30	2.27	12536.11
	subbase	4.41	7.73	43297.63
Station: 9+600.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	0.00	0.00	1855217.98
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	199.78	4014.52	1889962.96
	topeka	0.31	7.10	2933.70
	binder	0.31	7.22	2993.09
	base	1.30	30.14	12566.25
	subbase	4.41	102.49	43400.12
Station: 9+625.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	0.00	0.00	1855217.98
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	280.77	6020.04	1895983.00
	topeka	0.31	7.63	2941.33
	binder	0.31	7.77	3000.85
	base	1.30	32.41	12598.66
	subbase	4.41	110.21	43510.33
Station: 9+650.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	0.00	0.00	1855217.98
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	340.26	7770.71	1903753.72
	topeka	0.31	7.63	2948.96
	binder	0.31	7.77	3008.62
	base	1.30	32.41	12631.08
	subbase	4.41	110.21	43620.55
Station: 9+675.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	0.00	0.00	1855217.98
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	373.95	8928.45	1912682.16
	topeka	0.31	7.63	2956.59
	binder	0.31	7.77	3016.38
	base	1.30	32.41	12663.49
	subbase	4.41	110.21	43730.76
Station: 9+700.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	0.00	0.00	1855217.98
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	393.08	9590.74	1922272.90
	topeka	0.31	7.63	2964.22
	binder	0.31	7.77	3024.15
	base	1.30	32.41	12695.90
	subbase	4.41	110.21	43840.97
Station: 9+725.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	0.00	0.00	1855217.98
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	404.48	9978.99	1932251.89
	topeka	0.31	7.63	2971.85
	binder	0.31	7.77	3031.91

	base	1.30	32.41	12728.32
	subbase	4.41	110.21	43951.19
Station: 9+750.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	0.00	0.00	1855217.98
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	412.95	10235.53	1942487.42
	topeka	0.31	7.63	2979.48
	binder	0.31	7.77	3039.68
	base	1.30	32.41	12760.73
	subbase	4.41	110.21	44061.40
Station: 9+775.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	0.00	0.02	1855218.00
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	424.21	10490.16	1952977.58
	topeka	0.31	7.63	2987.11
	binder	0.31	7.77	3047.44
	base	1.30	32.41	12793.14
	subbase	4.41	110.21	44171.61
Station: 9+800.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	0.00	0.02	1855218.02
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	422.03	10599.79	1963577.37
	topeka	0.31	7.63	2994.74
	binder	0.31	7.77	3055.21
	base	1.30	32.41	12825.56
	subbase	4.41	110.21	44281.82
Station: 9+825.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	0.00	0.00	1855218.02
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	456.88	10998.56	1974575.92
	topeka	0.31	7.63	3002.37
	binder	0.31	7.77	3062.97
	base	1.30	32.41	12857.97
	subbase	4.41	110.21	44392.04
Station: 9+850.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	0.00	0.00	1855218.02
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	456.66	11424.40	1986000.32
	topeka	0.31	7.63	3010.00
	binder	0.31	7.77	3070.74
	base	1.30	32.41	12890.39
	subbase	4.41	110.21	44502.25
Station: 9+853.204				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	0.00	0.00	1855218.02
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	452.50	1456.56	1987456.88
	topeka	0.31	0.98	3010.97
	binder	0.31	1.00	3071.74
	base	1.30	4.16	12894.54
	subbase	4.41	14.13	44516.39

Station: 9+875.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	0.00	0.00	1855218.02
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	377.09	9042.19	1996499.07
	topeka	0.31	6.65	3017.63
	binder	0.31	6.77	3078.51
	base	1.30	28.26	12922.80
	subbase	4.41	96.09	44612.47
Station: 9+900.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	0.00	0.00	1855218.02
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	279.58	8211.56	2004710.64
	topeka	0.31	7.63	3025.26
	binder	0.31	7.77	3086.27
	base	1.30	32.41	12955.21
	subbase	4.41	110.21	44722.69
Station: 9+925.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	0.00	0.00	1855218.03
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	197.56	5967.20	2010677.83
	topeka	0.31	7.63	3032.89
	binder	0.31	7.77	3094.04
	base	1.30	32.41	12987.63
	subbase	4.41	110.21	44832.90
Station: 9+950.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	0.00	0.00	1855218.03
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	130.45	4101.26	2014779.09
	topeka	0.31	7.63	3040.52
	binder	0.31	7.77	3101.80
	base	1.30	32.41	13020.04
	subbase	4.41	110.21	44943.11
Station: 9+975.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	0.00	0.00	1855218.04
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	78.63	2613.96	2017393.05
	topeka	0.31	7.63	3048.15
	binder	0.31	7.77	3109.57
	base	1.30	32.41	13052.45
	subbase	4.41	110.21	45053.33
Station: 10+000.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	0.00	0.00	1855218.04
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	59.36	1727.81	2019120.85
	topeka	0.31	7.63	3055.78
	binder	0.31	7.77	3117.33
	base	1.30	32.41	13084.87
	subbase	4.41	110.21	45163.54
Station: 10+025.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	0.00	0.00	1855218.04

	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	63.46	1539.89	2020660.75
	topeka	0.31	7.63	3063.41
	binder	0.31	7.77	3125.10
	base	1.30	32.41	13117.28
	subbase	4.41	110.21	45273.75
Station: 10+050.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	0.00	0.00	1855218.04
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	100.61	2057.67	2022718.41
	topeka	0.31	7.63	3071.04
	binder	0.31	7.77	3132.86
	base	1.30	32.41	13149.69
	subbase	4.41	110.21	45383.97
Station: 10+075.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	0.00	0.00	1855218.04
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	80.36	2266.21	2024984.62
	topeka	0.31	7.63	3078.67
	binder	0.31	7.77	3140.63
	base	1.30	32.41	13182.11
	subbase	4.41	110.21	45494.18
Station: 10+100.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	0.00	0.00	1855218.05
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	81.69	2025.28	2027009.90
	topeka	0.31	7.63	3086.30
	binder	0.31	7.77	3148.39
	base	1.30	32.41	13214.52
	subbase	4.41	110.21	45604.39
Station: 10+125.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	0.00	0.00	1855218.05
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	75.88	1969.34	2028979.24
	topeka	0.31	7.63	3093.93
	binder	0.31	7.77	3156.16
	base	1.30	32.41	13246.93
	subbase	4.41	110.21	45714.61
Station: 10+129.656				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	0.00	0.00	1855218.05
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	80.20	363.32	2029342.56
	topeka	0.31	1.42	3095.35
	binder	0.31	1.45	3157.61
	base	1.30	6.04	13252.97
	subbase	4.41	20.54	45735.14
Station: 10+145.942				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	0.00	0.00	1855218.05
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	64.00	1173.40	2030515.96
	topeka	0.31	4.97	3100.32

	binder	0.31	5.06	3162.66
	base	1.29	21.09	13274.06
	subbase	4.38	71.55	45806.69
Station: 10+148.654				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	0.00	0.00	1855218.05
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	58.47	166.09	2030682.05
	topeka	0.31	0.83	3101.15
	binder	0.31	0.84	3163.50
	base	1.29	3.51	13277.57
	subbase	4.38	11.88	45818.58
Station: 10+150.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	0.00	0.00	1855218.05
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	55.89	76.97	2030759.02
	topeka	0.31	0.41	3101.56
	binder	0.31	0.42	3163.92
	base	1.29	1.74	13279.31
	subbase	4.39	5.90	45824.48
Station: 10+170.370				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	0.00	0.01	1855218.06
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	25.32	827.14	2031586.16
	topeka	0.31	6.22	3107.77
	binder	0.31	6.33	3170.25
	base	1.30	26.39	13305.70
	subbase	4.41	89.61	45914.09
Station: 10+186.656				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	0.00	0.00	1855218.06
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	7.00	263.25	2031849.41
	topeka	0.31	4.97	3112.74
	binder	0.31	5.06	3175.31
	base	1.30	21.15	13326.85
	subbase	4.44	72.09	45986.18
Station: 10+200.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	5.19	34.65	1855252.72
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.00	46.74	2031896.15
	topeka	0.31	4.07	3116.82
	binder	0.31	4.15	3179.46
	base	1.30	17.37	13344.21
	subbase	4.47	59.42	46045.60
Station: 10+202.942				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	8.23	19.75	1855272.47
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.00	0.00	2031896.15
	topeka	0.31	0.90	3117.72
	binder	0.31	0.92	3180.37
	base	1.30	3.83	13348.05

	subbase	4.47	13.14	46058.74
Station: 10+227.370				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	41.51	607.55	1855880.02
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.00	0.00	2031896.15
	topeka	0.31	7.46	3125.18
	binder	0.31	7.61	3187.99
	base	1.31	31.92	13379.97
	subbase	4.53	109.94	46168.69
Station: 10+250.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	71.37	1277.21	1857157.23
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.00	0.00	2031896.15
	topeka	0.31	6.92	3132.10
	binder	0.31	7.06	3195.04
	base	1.31	29.65	13409.61
	subbase	4.53	102.51	46271.20
Station: 10+300.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	96.34	4192.83	1861350.06
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.00	0.00	2031896.15
	topeka	0.31	15.28	3147.38
	binder	0.31	15.59	3210.64
	base	1.31	65.50	13475.11
	subbase	4.53	226.50	46497.70
Station: 10+350.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	99.70	4901.11	1866251.17
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.00	0.00	2031896.15
	topeka	0.31	15.28	3162.66
	binder	0.31	15.59	3226.23
	base	1.31	65.50	13540.61
	subbase	4.53	226.50	46724.20
Station: 10+400.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	95.79	4887.26	1871138.43
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.00	0.00	2031896.16
	topeka	0.31	15.28	3177.94
	binder	0.31	15.59	3241.82
	base	1.31	65.50	13606.11
	subbase	4.53	226.50	46950.70
Station: 10+450.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	93.55	4733.46	1875871.89
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.00	0.02	2031896.18
	topeka	0.31	15.28	3193.22
	binder	0.31	15.59	3257.42
	base	1.31	65.50	13671.61
	subbase	4.53	226.50	47177.20
Station: 10+500.000				

	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	101.78	4883.25	1880755.14
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.00	0.02	2031896.20
	topeka	0.31	15.28	3208.50
	binder	0.31	15.59	3273.01
	base	1.31	65.50	13737.11
	subbase	4.53	226.50	47403.70
Station: 10+550.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	102.75	5113.33	1885868.47
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.00	0.00	2031896.20
	topeka	0.31	15.28	3223.79
	binder	0.31	15.59	3288.61
	base	1.31	65.50	13802.61
	subbase	4.53	226.50	47630.20
Station: 10+600.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	92.33	4876.97	1890745.44
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.00	0.00	2031896.20
	topeka	0.31	15.28	3239.07
	binder	0.31	15.59	3304.20
	base	1.31	65.50	13868.11
	subbase	4.53	226.50	47856.70
Station: 10+650.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	51.71	3600.84	1894346.28
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.46	11.60	2031907.80
	topeka	0.31	15.28	3254.35
	binder	0.31	15.59	3319.79
	base	1.31	65.50	13933.61
	subbase	4.53	226.50	48083.20
Station: 10+700.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	0.00	1292.72	1895639.00
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	216.95	5435.28	2037343.08
	topeka	0.31	15.28	3269.63
	binder	0.31	15.59	3335.39
	base	1.31	65.50	13999.11
	subbase	4.53	226.50	48309.70
Station: 10+750.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	0.00	0.00	1895639.00
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	227.70	11116.12	2048459.20
	topeka	0.31	15.28	3284.91
	binder	0.31	15.59	3350.98
	base	1.31	65.50	14064.61
	subbase	4.53	226.50	48536.20
Station: 10+800.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	0.00	0.00	1895639.00
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	186.73	10360.80	2058819.99

	topeka	0.31	15.28	3300.19
	binder	0.31	15.59	3366.57
	base	1.31	65.50	14130.11
	subbase	4.53	226.50	48762.70
Station: 10+850.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	0.00	0.04	1895639.04
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	126.14	7821.95	2066641.94
	topeka	0.31	15.28	3315.47
	binder	0.31	15.59	3382.17
	base	1.31	65.50	14195.61
	subbase	4.53	226.50	48989.20
Station: 10+900.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	0.00	0.04	1895639.08
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	88.12	5356.65	2071998.59
	topeka	0.31	15.28	3330.75
	binder	0.31	15.59	3397.76
	base	1.31	65.50	14261.11
	subbase	4.53	226.50	49215.70
Station: 10+950.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	0.00	0.00	1895639.08
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	58.72	3671.11	2075669.70
	topeka	0.31	15.28	3346.04
	binder	0.31	15.59	3413.36
	base	1.31	65.50	14326.61
	subbase	4.53	226.50	49442.20
Station: 11+000.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	0.00	0.00	1895639.08
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	35.90	2365.64	2078035.34
	topeka	0.31	15.28	3361.32
	binder	0.31	15.59	3428.95
	base	1.31	65.50	14392.11
	subbase	4.53	226.50	49668.70
Station: 11+050.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	10.44	261.08	1895900.16
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.00	897.60	2078932.94
	topeka	0.31	15.28	3376.60
	binder	0.31	15.59	3444.54
	base	1.31	65.50	14457.61
	subbase	4.53	226.50	49895.20
Station: 11+100.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	58.55	1724.92	1897625.08
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.00	0.01	2078932.96
	topeka	0.31	15.28	3391.88
	binder	0.31	15.59	3460.14

	base	1.31	65.50	14523.11
	subbase	4.53	226.50	50121.70
Station: 11+150.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	87.98	3663.44	1901288.52
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.00	0.00	2078932.96
	topeka	0.31	15.28	3407.16
	binder	0.31	15.59	3475.73
	base	1.31	65.50	14588.61
	subbase	4.53	226.50	50348.20
Station: 11+200.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	101.71	4742.43	1906030.96
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.00	0.00	2078932.96
	topeka	0.31	15.28	3422.44
	binder	0.31	15.59	3491.32
	base	1.31	65.50	14654.11
	subbase	4.53	226.50	50574.70
Station: 11+250.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	85.86	4689.24	1910720.19
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.00	0.04	2078933.00
	topeka	0.31	15.28	3437.72
	binder	0.31	15.59	3506.92
	base	1.31	65.50	14719.61
	subbase	4.53	226.50	50801.20
Station: 11+300.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	42.78	3215.91	1913936.10
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.00	0.04	2078933.05
	topeka	0.31	15.28	3453.00
	binder	0.31	15.59	3522.51
	base	1.31	65.50	14785.11
	subbase	4.53	226.50	51027.70
Station: 11+350.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	11.09	1346.81	1915282.91
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.00	0.08	2078933.13
	topeka	0.31	15.28	3468.29
	binder	0.31	15.59	3538.11
	base	1.31	65.50	14850.61
	subbase	4.53	226.50	51254.20
Station: 11+400.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	7.56	466.22	1915749.12
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.00	0.08	2078933.21
	topeka	0.31	15.28	3483.57
	binder	0.31	15.59	3553.70
	base	1.31	65.50	14916.11
	subbase	4.53	226.50	51480.70

Station: 11+450.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	53.65	1530.29	1917279.42
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.00	0.00	2078933.21
	topeka	0.31	15.28	3498.85
	binder	0.31	15.59	3569.29
	base	1.31	65.50	14981.61
	subbase	4.53	226.50	51707.20
Station: 11+500.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	117.57	4280.73	1921560.14
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.00	0.00	2078933.21
	topeka	0.31	15.28	3514.13
	binder	0.31	15.59	3584.89
	base	1.31	65.50	15047.11
	subbase	4.53	226.50	51933.70
Station: 11+518.377				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	149.38	2452.85	1924013.00
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.00	0.00	2078933.21
	topeka	0.31	5.62	3519.75
	binder	0.31	5.73	3590.62
	base	1.31	24.07	15071.19
	subbase	4.53	83.25	52016.95
Station: 11+542.805				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	191.45	4162.97	1928175.97
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.00	0.00	2078933.21
	topeka	0.31	7.46	3527.21
	binder	0.31	7.61	3598.23
	base	1.30	31.92	15103.11
	subbase	4.47	109.94	52126.89
Station: 11+550.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	205.03	1426.28	1929602.25
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.00	0.00	2078933.21
	topeka	0.31	2.20	3529.41
	binder	0.31	2.24	3600.47
	base	1.30	9.37	15112.48
	subbase	4.46	32.12	52159.01
Station: 11+559.091				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	223.39	1947.38	1931549.63
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.00	0.00	2078933.21
	topeka	0.31	2.78	3532.18
	binder	0.31	2.83	3603.30
	base	1.30	11.83	15124.31
	subbase	4.44	40.44	52199.45
Station: 11+575.377				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	244.62	3810.92	1935360.56

	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.00	0.00	2078933.21
	topeka	0.31	4.97	3537.15
	binder	0.31	5.06	3608.36
	base	1.30	21.15	15145.45
	subbase	4.41	72.09	52271.54
Station: 11+597.093				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	257.50	5452.05	1940812.60
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.00	0.00	2078933.21
	topeka	0.31	6.63	3543.78
	binder	0.31	6.74	3615.10
	base	1.29	28.13	15173.58
	subbase	4.38	95.52	52367.06
Station: 11+599.805				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	261.75	704.21	1941516.81
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.00	0.00	2078933.21
	topeka	0.31	0.83	3544.61
	binder	0.31	0.84	3615.94
	base	1.29	3.51	15177.09
	subbase	4.38	11.88	52378.94
Station: 11+600.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	262.10	51.01	1941567.82
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.00	0.00	2078933.21
	topeka	0.31	0.06	3544.67
	binder	0.31	0.06	3616.00
	base	1.29	0.25	15177.35
	subbase	4.38	0.85	52379.79
Station: 11+616.091				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	289.45	4435.94	1946003.76
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.00	0.00	2078933.21
	topeka	0.31	4.91	3549.58
	binder	0.31	5.00	3621.00
	base	1.30	20.84	15198.18
	subbase	4.41	70.70	52450.49
Station: 11+625.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	301.88	2634.08	1948637.84
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.00	0.00	2078933.21
	topeka	0.31	2.72	3552.30
	binder	0.31	2.77	3623.77
	base	1.30	11.55	15209.73
	subbase	4.41	39.30	52489.79
Station: 11+650.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	335.68	7966.21	1956604.05
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.00	0.00	2078933.21
	topeka	0.31	7.63	3559.93

	binder	0.31	7.77	3631.53
	base	1.30	32.41	15242.15
	subbase	4.41	110.21	52600.00
Station: 11+675.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	357.97	8671.31	1965275.36
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.00	0.00	2078933.21
	topeka	0.31	7.63	3567.56
	binder	0.31	7.77	3639.30
	base	1.30	32.41	15274.56
	subbase	4.41	110.21	52710.22
Station: 11+700.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	364.90	9039.37	1974314.73
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.00	0.00	2078933.22
	topeka	0.31	7.63	3575.19
	binder	0.31	7.77	3647.06
	base	1.30	32.41	15306.97
	subbase	4.41	110.21	52820.43
Station: 11+721.139				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	375.76	7830.38	1982145.11
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.00	0.00	2078933.22
	topeka	0.31	6.45	3581.64
	binder	0.31	6.57	3653.63
	base	1.30	27.41	15334.38
	subbase	4.41	93.19	52913.62
Station: 11+725.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	377.60	1454.37	1983599.48
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.00	0.00	2078933.22
	topeka	0.31	1.18	3582.82
	binder	0.31	1.20	3654.83
	base	1.30	5.01	15339.39
	subbase	4.41	17.03	52930.65
Station: 11+750.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	388.05	9573.72	1993173.20
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.00	0.00	2078933.22
	topeka	0.31	7.63	3590.45
	binder	0.31	7.77	3662.59
	base	1.30	32.41	15371.80
	subbase	4.41	110.21	53040.87
Station: 11+775.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	394.30	9784.57	2002957.77
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.00	0.00	2078933.22
	topeka	0.31	7.63	3598.08
	binder	0.31	7.77	3670.36
	base	1.30	32.41	15404.22

	subbase	4.41	110.21	53151.08
Station: 11+800.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	391.18	9826.86	2012784.62
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.00	0.00	2078933.22
	topeka	0.31	7.63	3605.71
	binder	0.31	7.77	3678.12
	base	1.30	32.41	15436.63
	subbase	4.41	110.21	53261.29
Station: 11+825.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	378.12	9626.38	2022411.00
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.00	0.00	2078933.22
	topeka	0.31	7.63	3613.34
	binder	0.31	7.77	3685.89
	base	1.30	32.41	15469.04
	subbase	4.41	110.21	53371.51
Station: 11+826.187				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	377.16	448.25	2022859.25
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.00	0.00	2078933.22
	topeka	0.31	0.36	3613.70
	binder	0.31	0.37	3686.26
	base	1.30	1.54	15470.58
	subbase	4.41	5.24	53376.74
Station: 11+842.473				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	361.95	6026.34	2028885.59
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.00	0.00	2078933.22
	topeka	0.31	4.97	3618.67
	binder	0.31	5.06	3691.31
	base	1.29	21.09	15491.67
	subbase	4.38	71.55	53448.29
Station: 11+845.185				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	361.08	980.57	2029866.16
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.00	0.00	2078933.22
	topeka	0.31	0.83	3619.50
	binder	0.31	0.84	3692.15
	base	1.29	3.51	15495.18
	subbase	4.38	11.88	53460.18
Station: 11+850.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	356.14	1726.69	2031592.85
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.00	0.00	2078933.22
	topeka	0.31	1.47	3620.97
	binder	0.31	1.49	3693.65
	base	1.29	6.23	15501.41
	subbase	4.39	21.12	53481.30
Station: 11+866.901				

	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	327.12	5773.99	2037366.83
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.00	0.00	2078933.22
	topeka	0.31	5.16	3626.12
	binder	0.31	5.25	3698.90
	base	1.30	21.90	15523.31
	subbase	4.41	74.39	53555.69
Station: 11+883.187				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	303.64	5136.14	2042502.97
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.00	0.00	2078933.22
	topeka	0.31	4.97	3631.10
	binder	0.31	5.06	3703.96
	base	1.30	21.15	15544.46
	subbase	4.44	72.09	53627.78
Station: 11+899.473				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	294.03	4866.72	2047369.69
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.00	0.00	2078933.22
	topeka	0.31	4.97	3636.07
	binder	0.31	5.07	3709.03
	base	1.30	21.20	15565.66
	subbase	4.47	72.56	53700.34
Station: 11+900.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	293.74	154.97	2047524.66
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.00	0.00	2078933.22
	topeka	0.31	0.16	3636.23
	binder	0.31	0.16	3709.19
	base	1.30	0.69	15566.34
	subbase	4.47	2.36	53702.70
Station: 11+923.901				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	281.21	6871.06	2054395.72
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.00	0.00	2078933.22
	topeka	0.31	7.30	3643.53
	binder	0.31	7.45	3716.64
	base	1.31	31.23	15597.58
	subbase	4.53	107.58	53810.28
Station: 11+950.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	255.55	7004.42	2061400.14
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.00	0.00	2078933.22
	topeka	0.31	7.98	3651.51
	binder	0.31	8.14	3724.78
	base	1.31	34.19	15631.77
	subbase	4.53	118.23	53928.51
Station: 12+000.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	193.71	11231.50	2072631.64
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.00	0.00	2078933.22

	topeka	0.31	15.28	3666.79
	binder	0.31	15.59	3740.37
	base	1.31	65.50	15697.27
	subbase	4.53	226.50	54155.01
Station: 12+050.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	112.51	7655.45	2080287.09
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.00	0.00	2078933.22
	topeka	0.31	15.28	3682.07
	binder	0.31	15.59	3755.96
	base	1.31	65.50	15762.77
	subbase	4.53	226.50	54381.51
Station: 12+100.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	88.63	5028.53	2085315.62
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.00	0.00	2078933.22
	topeka	0.31	15.28	3697.35
	binder	0.31	15.59	3771.56
	base	1.31	65.50	15828.27
	subbase	4.53	226.50	54608.01
Station: 12+150.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	3.46	2302.34	2087617.96
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	3.45	86.18	2079019.39
	topeka	0.31	15.28	3712.63
	binder	0.31	15.59	3787.15
	base	1.31	65.50	15893.77
	subbase	4.53	226.50	54834.51
Station: 12+200.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	0.00	86.51	2087704.47
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	102.76	2655.21	2081674.60
	topeka	0.31	15.28	3727.92
	binder	0.31	15.59	3802.75
	base	1.31	65.50	15959.27
	subbase	4.53	226.50	55061.01
Station: 12+250.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	0.00	0.00	2087704.47
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	207.67	7760.89	2089435.49
	topeka	0.31	15.28	3743.20
	binder	0.31	15.59	3818.34
	base	1.31	65.50	16024.77
	subbase	4.53	226.50	55287.51
Station: 12+300.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	0.00	0.00	2087704.47
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	282.14	12245.36	2101680.85
	topeka	0.31	15.28	3758.48
	binder	0.31	15.59	3833.93

	base	1.31	65.50	16090.27
	subbase	4.53	226.50	55514.01
Station: 12+350.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	0.00	0.15	2087704.63
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	286.67	14220.17	2115901.02
	topeka	0.31	15.28	3773.76
	binder	0.31	15.59	3849.53
	base	1.31	65.50	16155.77
	subbase	4.53	226.50	55740.51
Station: 12+400.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	0.00	0.15	2087704.78
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	384.49	16778.95	2132679.97
	topeka	0.31	15.28	3789.04
	binder	0.31	15.59	3865.12
	base	1.31	65.50	16221.27
	subbase	4.53	226.50	55967.01
Station: 12+450.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	0.00	0.00	2087704.78
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	593.45	24448.54	2157128.51
	topeka	0.31	15.28	3804.32
	binder	0.31	15.59	3880.71
	base	1.31	65.50	16286.77
	subbase	4.53	226.50	56193.51
Station: 12+500.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	0.00	0.00	2087704.78
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	618.32	30294.25	2187422.77
	topeka	0.31	15.28	3819.60
	binder	0.31	15.59	3896.31
	base	1.31	65.50	16352.27
	subbase	4.53	226.50	56420.01
Station: 12+550.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	0.00	0.00	2087704.78
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	317.75	23401.65	2210824.41
	topeka	0.31	15.28	3834.88
	binder	0.31	15.59	3911.90
	base	1.31	65.50	16417.77
	subbase	4.53	226.50	56646.51
Station: 12+600.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	0.00	0.00	2087704.79
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	73.48	9780.78	2220605.19
	topeka	0.31	15.28	3850.17
	binder	0.31	15.59	3927.50
	base	1.31	65.50	16483.27
	subbase	4.53	226.50	56873.01

Station: 12+650.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	38.84	971.11	2088675.90
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.00	1837.12	2222442.30
	topeka	0.31	15.28	3865.45
	binder	0.31	15.59	3943.09
	base	1.31	65.50	16548.77
	subbase	4.53	226.50	57099.51
Station: 12+700.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	38.30	1928.65	2090604.54
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.00	0.00	2222442.30
	topeka	0.31	15.28	3880.73
	binder	0.31	15.59	3958.68
	base	1.31	65.50	16614.27
	subbase	4.53	226.50	57326.01
Station: 12+750.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	18.99	1432.24	2092036.79
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.00	0.04	2222442.34
	topeka	0.31	15.28	3896.01
	binder	0.31	15.59	3974.28
	base	1.31	65.50	16679.77
	subbase	4.53	226.50	57552.51
Station: 12+800.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	33.34	1308.25	2093345.04
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.00	0.04	2222442.38
	topeka	0.31	15.28	3911.29
	binder	0.31	15.59	3989.87
	base	1.31	65.50	16745.27
	subbase	4.53	226.50	57779.01
Station: 12+850.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	115.92	3731.51	2097076.56
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.00	0.00	2222442.38
	topeka	0.31	15.28	3926.57
	binder	0.31	15.59	4005.46
	base	1.31	65.50	16810.77
	subbase	4.53	226.50	58005.51
Station: 12+900.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	172.18	7202.48	2104279.04
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.00	0.00	2222442.38
	topeka	0.31	15.28	3941.85
	binder	0.31	15.59	4021.06
	base	1.31	65.50	16876.27
	subbase	4.53	226.50	58232.01
Station: 12+950.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	199.11	9282.16	2113561.20

	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.00	0.00	2222442.38
	topeka	0.31	15.28	3957.13
	binder	0.31	15.59	4036.65
	base	1.31	65.50	16941.77
	subbase	4.53	226.50	58458.51
Station: 13+000.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	256.54	11391.11	2124952.30
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.00	0.00	2222442.38
	topeka	0.31	15.28	3972.42
	binder	0.31	15.59	4052.25
	base	1.31	65.50	17007.27
	subbase	4.53	226.50	58685.01
Station: 13+050.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	209.02	11639.02	2136591.33
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.00	0.00	2222442.38
	topeka	0.31	15.28	3987.70
	binder	0.31	15.59	4067.84
	base	1.31	65.50	17072.77
	subbase	4.53	226.50	58911.51
Station: 13+100.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	128.89	8447.71	2145039.04
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.00	0.00	2222442.38
	topeka	0.31	15.28	4002.98
	binder	0.31	15.59	4083.43
	base	1.31	65.50	17138.27
	subbase	4.53	226.50	59138.01
Station: 13+150.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	285.91	10369.93	2155408.97
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.00	0.00	2222442.38
	topeka	0.31	15.28	4018.26
	binder	0.31	15.59	4099.03
	base	1.31	65.50	17203.77
	subbase	4.53	226.50	59364.51
Station: 13+200.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	429.22	17878.23	2173287.20
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.00	0.00	2222442.38
	topeka	0.31	15.28	4033.54
	binder	0.31	15.59	4114.62
	base	1.31	65.50	17269.27
	subbase	4.53	226.50	59591.01
Station: 13+250.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	205.72	15873.56	2189160.76
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.00	0.00	2222442.38
	topeka	0.31	15.28	4048.82

	binder	0.31	15.59	4130.21
	base	1.31	65.50	17334.77
	subbase	4.53	226.50	59817.51
Station: 13+300.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	0.00	5143.11	2194303.87
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	5.57	139.15	2222581.52
	topeka	0.31	15.28	4064.10
	binder	0.31	15.59	4145.81
	base	1.31	65.50	17400.27
	subbase	4.53	226.50	60044.01
Station: 13+350.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	0.22	5.57	2194309.44
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	10.91	411.98	2222993.51
	topeka	0.31	15.28	4079.38
	binder	0.31	15.59	4161.40
	base	1.31	65.50	17465.77
	subbase	4.53	226.50	60270.51
Station: 13+400.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	0.00	5.57	2194315.00
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	28.78	992.43	2223985.94
	topeka	0.31	15.28	4094.67
	binder	0.31	15.59	4177.00
	base	1.31	65.50	17531.27
	subbase	4.53	226.50	60497.01
Station: 13+450.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	0.64	15.92	2194330.93
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	15.52	1107.51	2225093.44
	topeka	0.31	15.28	4109.95
	binder	0.31	15.59	4192.59
	base	1.31	65.50	17596.77
	subbase	4.53	226.50	60723.51
Station: 13+500.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	0.00	15.92	2194346.85
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	148.20	4093.03	2229186.47
	topeka	0.31	15.28	4125.23
	binder	0.31	15.59	4208.18
	base	1.31	65.50	17662.27
	subbase	4.53	226.50	60950.01
Station: 13+550.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	0.00	0.00	2194346.85
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	310.37	11464.39	2240650.86
	topeka	0.31	15.28	4140.51
	binder	0.31	15.59	4223.78
	base	1.31	65.50	17727.77

	subbase	4.53	226.50	61176.51
Station: 13+557.724				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	0.00	0.00	2194346.85
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	295.39	2339.36	2242990.23
	topeka	0.31	2.36	4142.87
	binder	0.31	2.41	4226.19
	base	1.31	10.12	17737.88
	subbase	4.53	34.99	61211.50
Station: 13+582.152				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	0.00	0.00	2194346.85
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	239.59	6534.34	2249524.56
	topeka	0.31	7.46	4150.33
	binder	0.31	7.61	4233.80
	base	1.30	31.92	17769.81
	subbase	4.47	109.94	61321.44
Station: 13+598.438				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	0.00	0.00	2194346.85
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	221.30	3752.99	2253277.56
	topeka	0.31	4.97	4155.31
	binder	0.31	5.07	4238.86
	base	1.30	21.20	17791.01
	subbase	4.44	72.56	61394.01
Station: 13+600.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	0.00	0.00	2194346.85
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	220.41	344.97	2253622.52
	topeka	0.31	0.48	4155.78
	binder	0.31	0.49	4239.35
	base	1.30	2.03	17793.04
	subbase	4.44	6.93	61400.94
Station: 13+614.724				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	0.00	0.00	2194346.85
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	241.31	3399.13	2257021.65
	topeka	0.31	4.49	4160.28
	binder	0.31	4.58	4243.92
	base	1.30	19.12	17812.15
	subbase	4.41	65.16	61466.10
Station: 13+636.440				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	0.00	0.00	2194346.85
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	307.50	5959.07	2262980.72
	topeka	0.31	6.63	4166.90
	binder	0.31	6.74	4250.67
	base	1.29	28.13	17840.28
	subbase	4.38	95.52	61561.61
Station: 13+639.152				

	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	0.00	0.00	2194346.85
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	315.70	845.18	2263825.90
	topeka	0.31	0.83	4167.73
	binder	0.31	0.84	4251.51
	base	1.29	3.51	17843.79
	subbase	4.38	11.88	61573.50
Station: 13+650.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	0.00	0.00	2194346.85
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	346.57	3625.52	2267451.42
	topeka	0.31	3.31	4171.04
	binder	0.31	3.37	4254.88
	base	1.30	14.04	17857.83
	subbase	4.40	47.59	61621.09
Station: 13+655.438				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	0.00	0.00	2194346.85
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	360.53	1922.62	2269374.05
	topeka	0.31	1.66	4172.70
	binder	0.31	1.69	4256.57
	base	1.30	7.05	17864.88
	subbase	4.41	23.96	61645.05
Station: 13+675.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	0.00	0.00	2194346.85
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	387.84	7391.95	2276765.99
	topeka	0.31	5.97	4178.67
	binder	0.31	6.08	4262.64
	base	1.30	25.36	17890.24
	subbase	4.41	86.24	61731.29
Station: 13+700.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	0.00	0.00	2194346.85
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	348.21	9307.89	2286073.88
	topeka	0.31	7.63	4186.30
	binder	0.31	7.77	4270.41
	base	1.30	32.41	17922.66
	subbase	4.41	110.21	61841.50
Station: 13+725.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	0.42	5.06	2194351.90
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	331.18	8611.09	2294684.98
	topeka	0.31	7.63	4193.93
	binder	0.31	7.77	4278.17
	base	1.30	32.41	17955.07
	subbase	4.41	110.21	61951.71
Station: 13+750.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	0.00	5.06	2194356.96
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	549.41	11122.61	2305807.58

	topeka	0.31	7.63	4201.56
	binder	0.31	7.77	4285.94
	base	1.30	32.41	17987.48
	subbase	4.41	110.21	62061.93
Station: 13+775.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	0.00	0.00	2194356.96
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	814.19	17160.86	2322968.45
	topeka	0.31	7.63	4209.19
	binder	0.31	7.77	4293.70
	base	1.30	32.41	18019.90
	subbase	4.41	110.21	62172.14
Station: 13+800.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	0.00	0.00	2194356.96
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	869.84	21154.34	2344122.79
	topeka	0.31	7.63	4216.82
	binder	0.31	7.77	4301.47
	base	1.30	32.41	18052.31
	subbase	4.41	110.21	62282.35
Station: 13+807.344				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	0.00	0.00	2194356.96
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	860.02	6352.12	2350474.91
	topeka	0.31	2.24	4219.06
	binder	0.31	2.28	4303.75
	base	1.30	9.52	18061.83
	subbase	4.41	32.40	62314.75
Station: 13+825.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	0.00	0.00	2194356.96
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	855.26	15202.57	2365677.47
	topeka	0.31	5.39	4224.45
	binder	0.31	5.48	4309.23
	base	1.30	22.89	18084.73
	subbase	4.41	77.84	62392.59
Station: 13+850.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	0.00	0.00	2194356.96
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	929.41	22387.86	2388065.34
	topeka	0.31	7.63	4232.08
	binder	0.31	7.77	4317.00
	base	1.30	32.41	18117.14
	subbase	4.41	110.21	62502.80
Station: 13+875.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	0.00	0.00	2194356.96
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	983.17	23966.78	2412032.12
	topeka	0.31	7.63	4239.71
	binder	0.31	7.77	4324.76

	base	1.30	32.41	18149.55
	subbase	4.41	110.21	62613.01
Station: 13+900.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	0.00	0.00	2194356.96
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	1006.91	24919.89	2436952.01
	topeka	0.31	7.63	4247.34
	binder	0.31	7.77	4332.53
	base	1.30	32.41	18181.97
	subbase	4.41	110.21	62723.23
Station: 13+925.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	0.00	0.00	2194356.96
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	1023.32	25409.78	2462361.79
	topeka	0.31	7.63	4254.97
	binder	0.31	7.77	4340.30
	base	1.30	32.41	18214.38
	subbase	4.41	110.21	62833.44
Station: 13+950.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	0.00	0.00	2194356.96
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	1040.10	25809.94	2488171.73
	topeka	0.31	7.63	4262.60
	binder	0.31	7.77	4348.06
	base	1.30	32.41	18246.79
	subbase	4.41	110.21	62943.65
Station: 13+959.250				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	0.00	0.00	2194356.96
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	1043.20	9635.41	2497807.14
	topeka	0.31	2.82	4265.43
	binder	0.31	2.87	4350.93
	base	1.30	12.00	18258.79
	subbase	4.41	40.80	62984.46
Station: 13+975.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	0.00	0.00	2194356.96
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	1043.89	16438.27	2514245.42
	topeka	0.31	4.81	4270.23
	binder	0.31	4.89	4355.82
	base	1.29	20.39	18279.18
	subbase	4.38	69.20	63053.66
Station: 13+975.536				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	0.00	0.00	2194356.96
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	1043.83	559.35	2514804.77
	topeka	0.31	0.16	4270.40
	binder	0.31	0.17	4355.99
	base	1.29	0.69	18279.88
	subbase	4.38	2.35	63056.01

Station: 13+978.248				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	0.00	0.00	2194356.96
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	1043.49	2830.81	2517635.58
	topeka	0.31	0.83	4271.22
	binder	0.31	0.84	4356.83
	base	1.29	3.51	18283.39
	subbase	4.38	11.88	63067.89
Station: 13+999.964				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	0.00	0.00	2194356.96
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	1002.99	22220.82	2539856.40
	topeka	0.31	6.63	4277.85
	binder	0.31	6.74	4363.57
	base	1.30	28.13	18311.52
	subbase	4.41	95.52	63163.41
Station: 14+000.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	0.00	0.00	2194356.96
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	1002.86	35.68	2539892.08
	topeka	0.31	0.01	4277.86
	binder	0.31	0.01	4363.59
	base	1.30	0.05	18311.56
	subbase	4.41	0.16	63163.56
Station: 14+016.250				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	0.00	0.00	2194356.96
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	925.57	15668.61	2555560.69
	topeka	0.31	4.96	4282.82
	binder	0.31	5.05	4368.64
	base	1.30	21.10	18332.66
	subbase	4.44	71.93	63235.50
Station: 14+032.536				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	0.00	0.00	2194356.96
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	824.03	14246.76	2569807.45
	topeka	0.31	4.97	4287.80
	binder	0.31	5.07	4373.70
	base	1.30	21.20	18353.86
	subbase	4.47	72.56	63308.06
Station: 14+050.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	0.00	0.06	2194357.02
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	694.06	13256.08	2583063.53
	topeka	0.31	5.34	4293.13
	binder	0.31	5.44	4379.14
	base	1.31	22.80	18376.67
	subbase	4.51	78.44	63386.50
Station: 14+056.964				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	0.00	0.02	2194357.04

	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	640.22	4646.23	2587709.76
	topeka	0.31	2.13	4295.26
	binder	0.31	2.17	4381.31
	base	1.31	9.12	18385.78
	subbase	4.53	31.48	63417.98
Station: 14+100.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	0.00	0.00	2194357.04
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	271.04	19608.19	2607317.95
	topeka	0.31	13.15	4308.41
	binder	0.31	13.42	4394.74
	base	1.31	56.38	18442.16
	subbase	4.53	194.95	63612.94
Station: 14+150.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	0.00	0.00	2194357.04
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	150.30	10533.39	2617851.34
	topeka	0.31	15.28	4323.69
	binder	0.31	15.59	4410.33
	base	1.31	65.50	18507.66
	subbase	4.53	226.50	63839.44
Station: 14+200.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	0.00	0.00	2194357.04
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	230.56	9521.44	2627372.78
	topeka	0.31	15.28	4338.97
	binder	0.31	15.59	4425.92
	base	1.31	65.50	18573.16
	subbase	4.53	226.50	64065.94
Station: 14+250.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	0.07	1.73	2194358.78
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	33.65	6605.29	2633978.06
	topeka	0.31	15.28	4354.26
	binder	0.31	15.59	4441.52
	base	1.31	65.50	18638.66
	subbase	4.53	226.50	64292.44
Station: 14+300.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	67.79	1696.53	2196055.31
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.00	841.36	2634819.42
	topeka	0.31	15.28	4369.54
	binder	0.31	15.59	4457.11
	base	1.31	65.50	18704.16
	subbase	4.53	226.50	64518.94
Station: 14+350.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	266.19	8349.43	2204404.74
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.00	0.18	2634819.61
	topeka	0.31	15.28	4384.82

	binder	0.31	15.59	4472.70
	base	1.31	65.50	18769.66
	subbase	4.53	226.50	64745.44
Station: 14+400.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	386.00	16304.58	2220709.32
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.00	0.18	2634819.79
	topeka	0.31	15.28	4400.10
	binder	0.31	15.59	4488.30
	base	1.31	65.50	18835.16
	subbase	4.53	226.50	64971.94
Station: 14+450.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	206.21	14805.23	2235514.56
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.03	0.72	2634820.50
	topeka	0.31	15.28	4415.38
	binder	0.31	15.59	4503.89
	base	1.31	65.50	18900.66
	subbase	4.53	226.50	65198.44
Station: 14+500.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	30.37	5914.62	2241429.18
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.00	0.72	2634821.22
	topeka	0.31	15.28	4430.66
	binder	0.31	15.59	4519.49
	base	1.31	65.50	18966.16
	subbase	4.53	226.50	65424.94
Station: 14+550.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	56.26	2165.74	2243594.91
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.00	0.00	2634821.22
	topeka	0.31	15.28	4445.94
	binder	0.31	15.59	4535.08
	base	1.31	65.50	19031.66
	subbase	4.53	226.50	65651.44
Station: 14+562.325				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	75.10	809.51	2244404.43
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.00	0.00	2634821.22
	topeka	0.31	3.77	4449.71
	binder	0.31	3.84	4538.92
	base	1.31	16.15	19047.81
	subbase	4.53	55.83	65707.27
Station: 14+600.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	92.36	3168.51	2247572.93
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.00	0.00	2634821.22
	topeka	0.31	11.51	4461.22
	binder	0.31	11.75	4550.67
	base	1.31	49.35	19097.16

	subbase	4.53	170.67	65877.94
Station: 14+650.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	140.66	5825.50	2253398.44
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.00	0.00	2634821.22
	topeka	0.31	15.28	4476.51
	binder	0.31	15.59	4566.27
	base	1.31	65.50	19162.66
	subbase	4.53	226.50	66104.44
Station: 14+700.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	88.44	5727.74	2259126.17
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.00	0.00	2634821.22
	topeka	0.31	15.28	4491.79
	binder	0.31	15.59	4581.86
	base	1.31	65.50	19228.16
	subbase	4.53	226.50	66330.94
Station: 14+750.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	64.40	3821.10	2262947.28
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.00	0.00	2634821.22
	topeka	0.31	15.28	4507.07
	binder	0.31	15.59	4597.45
	base	1.31	65.50	19293.66
	subbase	4.53	226.50	66557.44
Station: 14+794.897				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	33.17	2190.27	2265137.55
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.00	0.00	2634821.22
	topeka	0.31	13.72	4520.79
	binder	0.31	14.00	4611.46
	base	1.31	58.81	19352.47
	subbase	4.53	203.38	66760.82
Station: 14+800.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	29.68	160.37	2265297.92
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.00	0.00	2634821.22
	topeka	0.31	1.56	4522.35
	binder	0.31	1.59	4613.05
	base	1.31	6.68	19359.16
	subbase	4.52	23.08	66783.90
Station: 14+819.325				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	18.00	460.74	2265758.66
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.00	0.00	2634821.22
	topeka	0.31	5.90	4528.25
	binder	0.31	6.02	4619.07
	base	1.30	25.24	19384.39
	subbase	4.47	86.85	66870.75
Station: 14+835.611				

	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	14.92	268.08	2266026.74
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.00	0.00	2634821.22
	topeka	0.31	4.97	4533.23
	binder	0.31	5.07	4624.13
	base	1.30	21.20	19405.59
	subbase	4.44	72.56	66943.31
Station: 14+850.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	10.29	181.37	2266208.11
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.00	0.00	2634821.22
	topeka	0.31	4.39	4537.62
	binder	0.31	4.47	4628.61
	base	1.30	18.69	19424.28
	subbase	4.42	63.72	67007.03
Station: 14+851.897				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	9.62	18.88	2266226.99
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.00	0.00	2634821.22
	topeka	0.31	0.58	4538.20
	binder	0.31	0.59	4629.20
	base	1.30	2.46	19426.74
	subbase	4.41	8.37	67015.40
Station: 14+873.613				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	17.86	298.42	2266525.41
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.00	0.00	2634821.22
	topeka	0.31	6.63	4544.82
	binder	0.31	6.74	4635.94
	base	1.29	28.13	19454.87
	subbase	4.38	95.52	67110.91
Station: 14+875.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	19.08	25.62	2266551.03
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.00	0.00	2634821.22
	topeka	0.31	0.42	4545.25
	binder	0.31	0.43	4636.37
	base	1.29	1.79	19456.67
	subbase	4.38	6.08	67116.99
Station: 14+876.325				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	20.27	26.08	2266577.12
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.00	0.00	2634821.22
	topeka	0.31	0.40	4545.65
	binder	0.31	0.41	4636.78
	base	1.29	1.71	19458.38
	subbase	4.38	5.81	67122.80
Station: 14+892.611				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	37.49	468.28	2267045.39
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.00	0.00	2634821.22

	topeka	0.31	4.97	4550.62
	binder	0.31	5.06	4641.84
	base	1.30	21.09	19479.47
	subbase	4.41	71.55	67194.35
Station: 14+900.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	45.67	307.24	2267352.64
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.00	0.00	2634821.22
	topeka	0.31	2.26	4552.88
	binder	0.31	2.30	4644.13
	base	1.30	9.58	19489.05
	subbase	4.41	32.59	67226.94
Station: 14+925.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	65.79	1389.11	2268741.75
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.00	0.00	2634821.22
	topeka	0.31	7.63	4560.51
	binder	0.31	7.77	4651.90
	base	1.30	32.41	19521.46
	subbase	4.41	110.21	67337.16
Station: 14+950.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	89.41	1935.32	2270677.07
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.00	0.04	2634821.26
	topeka	0.31	7.63	4568.14
	binder	0.31	7.77	4659.66
	base	1.30	32.41	19553.88
	subbase	4.41	110.21	67447.37
Station: 14+975.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	121.03	2623.06	2273300.13
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.00	0.04	2634821.30
	topeka	0.31	7.63	4575.77
	binder	0.31	7.77	4667.43
	base	1.30	32.41	19586.29
	subbase	4.41	110.21	67557.58
Station: 14+999.018				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	162.78	3400.19	2276700.32
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.00	0.00	2634821.30
	topeka	0.31	7.33	4583.10
	binder	0.31	7.46	4674.89
	base	1.30	31.14	19617.43
	subbase	4.41	105.88	67663.47
Station: 15+000.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	163.46	160.16	2276860.48
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.00	0.00	2634821.30
	topeka	0.31	0.30	4583.40
	binder	0.31	0.30	4675.19

	base	1.30	1.27	19618.70
	subbase	4.41	4.33	67667.80
Station: 15+025.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	148.80	3895.28	2280755.76
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.02	0.29	2634821.59
	topeka	0.31	7.63	4591.03
	binder	0.31	7.77	4682.96
	base	1.30	32.41	19651.12
	subbase	4.41	110.21	67778.01
Station: 15+050.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	157.24	3819.00	2284574.76
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.00	0.29	2634821.88
	topeka	0.31	7.63	4598.66
	binder	0.31	7.77	4690.72
	base	1.30	32.41	19683.53
	subbase	4.41	110.21	67888.22
Station: 15+075.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	178.08	4186.37	2288761.13
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.00	0.00	2634821.88
	topeka	0.31	7.63	4606.29
	binder	0.31	7.77	4698.49
	base	1.30	32.41	19715.94
	subbase	4.41	110.21	67998.44
Station: 15+100.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	198.65	4705.14	2293466.28
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.00	0.00	2634821.88
	topeka	0.31	7.63	4613.92
	binder	0.31	7.77	4706.25
	base	1.30	32.41	19748.36
	subbase	4.41	110.21	68108.65
Station: 15+105.425				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	203.00	1089.52	2294555.79
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.00	0.00	2634821.88
	topeka	0.31	1.66	4615.57
	binder	0.31	1.69	4707.94
	base	1.30	7.04	19755.39
	subbase	4.41	23.93	68132.58
Station: 15+121.711				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	214.02	3395.11	2297950.90
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.00	0.00	2634821.88
	topeka	0.31	4.97	4620.54
	binder	0.31	5.06	4713.00
	base	1.29	21.09	19776.48
	subbase	4.38	71.55	68204.13

Station: 15+124.423				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	216.25	583.53	2298534.43
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.00	0.00	2634821.88
	topeka	0.31	0.83	4621.37
	binder	0.31	0.84	4713.84
	base	1.29	3.51	19779.99
	subbase	4.38	11.88	68216.02
Station: 15+146.139				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	232.66	4874.31	2303408.75
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.00	0.00	2634821.88
	topeka	0.31	6.63	4628.00
	binder	0.31	6.74	4720.58
	base	1.30	28.13	19808.12
	subbase	4.41	95.52	68311.53
Station: 15+150.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	235.33	903.35	2304312.10
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.00	0.00	2634821.88
	topeka	0.31	1.18	4629.18
	binder	0.31	1.20	4721.78
	base	1.30	5.01	19813.13
	subbase	4.42	17.05	68328.58
Station: 15+162.425				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	243.50	2974.81	2307286.91
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.00	0.00	2634821.88
	topeka	0.31	3.79	4632.97
	binder	0.31	3.86	4725.64
	base	1.30	16.14	19829.27
	subbase	4.44	55.04	68383.62
Station: 15+178.711				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	252.04	4035.12	2311322.03
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.00	0.00	2634821.88
	topeka	0.31	4.97	4637.94
	binder	0.31	5.07	4730.71
	base	1.30	21.20	19850.47
	subbase	4.47	72.56	68456.18
Station: 15+200.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	263.57	5488.43	2316810.46
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.00	0.00	2634821.88
	topeka	0.31	6.50	4644.45
	binder	0.31	6.63	4737.34
	base	1.31	27.81	19878.28
	subbase	4.52	95.72	68551.91
Station: 15+203.139				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	266.52	832.09	2317642.55

	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.00	0.00	2634821.88
	topeka	0.31	0.96	4645.41
	binder	0.31	0.98	4738.32
	base	1.31	4.11	19882.39
	subbase	4.53	14.21	68566.12
Station: 15+250.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	306.62	13428.84	2331071.39
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.02	0.50	2634822.38
	topeka	0.31	14.32	4659.73
	binder	0.31	14.61	4752.93
	base	1.31	61.39	19943.77
	subbase	4.53	212.28	68778.39
Station: 15+300.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	292.50	14978.14	2346049.53
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.00	0.53	2634822.91
	topeka	0.31	15.28	4675.01
	binder	0.31	15.59	4768.53
	base	1.31	65.50	20009.27
	subbase	4.53	226.50	69004.89
Station: 15+350.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	417.22	17742.95	2363792.48
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.00	0.00	2634822.91
	topeka	0.31	15.28	4690.29
	binder	0.31	15.59	4784.12
	base	1.31	65.50	20074.77
	subbase	4.53	226.50	69231.39
Station: 15+400.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	577.27	24862.05	2388654.53
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.00	0.00	2634822.91
	topeka	0.31	15.28	4705.57
	binder	0.31	15.59	4799.72
	base	1.31	65.50	20140.27
	subbase	4.53	226.50	69457.89
Station: 15+450.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	830.92	35204.60	2423859.13
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.00	0.00	2634822.91
	topeka	0.31	15.28	4720.85
	binder	0.31	15.59	4815.31
	base	1.31	65.50	20205.77
	subbase	4.53	226.50	69684.39
Station: 15+500.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	994.24	45628.93	2469488.07
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.00	0.00	2634822.91
	topeka	0.31	15.28	4736.13

	binder	0.31	15.59	4830.90
	base	1.31	65.50	20271.27
	subbase	4.53	226.50	69910.89
Station: 15+550.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	824.06	45457.42	2514945.49
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.00	0.00	2634822.91
	topeka	0.31	15.28	4751.42
	binder	0.31	15.59	4846.50
	base	1.31	65.50	20336.77
	subbase	4.53	226.50	70137.39
Station: 15+600.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	552.96	34425.46	2549370.95
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.00	0.00	2634822.91
	topeka	0.31	15.28	4766.70
	binder	0.31	15.59	4862.09
	base	1.31	65.50	20402.27
	subbase	4.53	226.50	70363.89
Station: 15+650.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	460.08	25325.95	2574696.90
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.00	0.00	2634822.92
	topeka	0.31	15.28	4781.98
	binder	0.31	15.59	4877.68
	base	1.31	65.50	20467.77
	subbase	4.53	226.50	70590.39
Station: 15+700.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	612.42	26812.35	2601509.25
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.00	0.00	2634822.92
	topeka	0.31	15.28	4797.26
	binder	0.31	15.59	4893.28
	base	1.31	65.50	20533.27
	subbase	4.53	226.50	70816.89
Station: 15+750.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	530.58	28574.81	2630084.06
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.00	0.03	2634822.96
	topeka	0.31	15.28	4812.54
	binder	0.31	15.59	4908.87
	base	1.31	65.50	20598.77
	subbase	4.53	226.50	71043.39
Station: 15+800.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	318.03	21215.22	2651299.29
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.00	0.03	2634822.99
	topeka	0.31	15.28	4827.82
	binder	0.31	15.59	4924.47
	base	1.31	65.50	20664.27

	subbase	4.53	226.50	71269.89
Station: 15+850.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	24.89	8573.05	2659872.33
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.00	0.00	2634822.99
	topeka	0.31	15.28	4843.10
	binder	0.31	15.59	4940.06
	base	1.31	65.50	20729.77
	subbase	4.53	226.50	71496.39
Station: 15+900.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	0.00	622.21	2660494.54
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	226.88	5672.12	2640495.11
	topeka	0.31	15.28	4858.38
	binder	0.31	15.59	4955.65
	base	1.31	65.50	20795.27
	subbase	4.53	226.50	71722.89
Station: 15+950.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	0.00	0.00	2660494.54
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	480.11	17674.86	2658169.97
	topeka	0.31	15.28	4873.67
	binder	0.31	15.59	4971.25
	base	1.31	65.50	20860.77
	subbase	4.53	226.50	71949.39
Station: 16+000.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	0.00	0.00	2660494.54
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	528.48	25214.80	2683384.77
	topeka	0.31	15.28	4888.95
	binder	0.31	15.59	4986.84
	base	1.31	65.50	20926.27
	subbase	4.53	226.50	72175.89
Station: 16+050.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	0.00	0.00	2660494.54
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	570.39	27471.68	2710856.45
	topeka	0.31	15.28	4904.23
	binder	0.31	15.59	5002.43
	base	1.31	65.50	20991.77
	subbase	4.53	226.50	72402.39
Station: 16+100.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	0.00	0.00	2660494.54
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	829.41	34994.83	2745851.28
	topeka	0.31	15.28	4919.51
	binder	0.31	15.59	5018.03
	base	1.31	65.50	21057.27
	subbase	4.53	226.50	72628.89
Station: 16+150.000				

	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	0.00	0.00	2660494.54
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	864.74	42353.79	2788205.07
	topeka	0.31	15.28	4934.79
	binder	0.31	15.59	5033.62
	base	1.31	65.50	21122.77
	subbase	4.53	226.50	72855.39
Station: 16+200.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	0.00	0.00	2660494.54
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	848.17	42822.84	2831027.91
	topeka	0.31	15.28	4950.07
	binder	0.31	15.59	5049.22
	base	1.31	65.50	21188.27
	subbase	4.53	226.50	73081.89
Station: 16+250.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	0.00	0.00	2660494.54
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	780.89	40726.63	2871754.54
	topeka	0.31	15.28	4965.35
	binder	0.31	15.59	5064.81
	base	1.31	65.50	21253.77
	subbase	4.53	226.50	73308.39
Station: 16+300.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	0.00	0.00	2660494.54
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	680.66	36538.76	2908293.30
	topeka	0.31	15.28	4980.63
	binder	0.31	15.59	5080.40
	base	1.31	65.50	21319.27
	subbase	4.53	226.50	73534.89
Station: 16+350.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	0.00	0.00	2660494.54
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	604.57	32130.72	2940424.02
	topeka	0.31	15.28	4995.92
	binder	0.31	15.59	5096.00
	base	1.31	65.50	21384.77
	subbase	4.53	226.50	73761.39
Station: 16+400.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	0.00	0.00	2660494.54
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	616.77	30533.48	2970957.50
	topeka	0.31	15.28	5011.20
	binder	0.31	15.59	5111.59
	base	1.31	65.50	21450.27
	subbase	4.53	226.50	73987.89
Station: 16+450.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	0.00	0.00	2660494.54
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	625.26	31050.58	3002008.08

	topeka	0.31	15.28	5026.48
	binder	0.31	15.59	5127.18
	base	1.31	65.50	21515.77
	subbase	4.53	226.50	74214.39
Station: 16+500.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	0.00	0.00	2660494.54
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	524.59	28746.12	3030754.21
	topeka	0.31	15.28	5041.76
	binder	0.31	15.59	5142.78
	base	1.31	65.50	21581.27
	subbase	4.53	226.50	74440.89
Station: 16+550.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	0.00	0.00	2660494.54
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	345.09	21741.99	3052496.20
	topeka	0.31	15.28	5057.04
	binder	0.31	15.59	5158.37
	base	1.31	65.50	21646.77
	subbase	4.53	226.50	74667.39
Station: 16+600.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	0.00	0.00	2660494.54
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	190.22	13382.81	3065879.01
	topeka	0.31	15.28	5072.32
	binder	0.31	15.59	5173.97
	base	1.31	65.50	21712.27
	subbase	4.53	226.50	74893.89
Station: 16+650.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	0.00	0.00	2660494.54
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	65.37	6389.68	3072268.69
	topeka	0.31	15.28	5087.60
	binder	0.31	15.59	5189.56
	base	1.31	65.50	21777.77
	subbase	4.53	226.50	75120.39
Station: 16+700.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	46.29	1157.25	2661651.79
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.00	1634.16	3073902.85
	topeka	0.31	15.28	5102.88
	binder	0.31	15.59	5205.15
	base	1.31	65.50	21843.27
	subbase	4.53	226.50	75346.89
Station: 16+750.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	264.86	7778.68	2669430.47
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.00	0.00	3073902.85
	topeka	0.31	15.28	5118.17
	binder	0.31	15.59	5220.75

	base	1.31	65.50	21908.77
	subbase	4.53	226.50	75573.39
Station: 16+800.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	656.67	23038.27	2692468.74
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.00	0.00	3073902.85
	topeka	0.31	15.28	5133.45
	binder	0.31	15.59	5236.34
	base	1.31	65.50	21974.27
	subbase	4.53	226.50	75799.89
Station: 16+850.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	828.35	37125.65	2729594.39
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.00	0.00	3073902.85
	topeka	0.31	15.28	5148.73
	binder	0.31	15.59	5251.93
	base	1.31	65.50	22039.77
	subbase	4.53	226.50	76026.39
Station: 16+900.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	957.95	44657.57	2774251.95
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.00	0.00	3073902.85
	topeka	0.31	15.28	5164.01
	binder	0.31	15.59	5267.53
	base	1.31	65.50	22105.27
	subbase	4.53	226.50	76252.89
Station: 16+950.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	959.51	47936.50	2822188.45
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.00	0.00	3073902.85
	topeka	0.31	15.28	5179.29
	binder	0.31	15.59	5283.12
	base	1.31	65.50	22170.77
	subbase	4.53	226.50	76479.39
Station: 17+000.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	843.52	45075.72	2867264.17
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.00	0.00	3073902.85
	topeka	0.31	15.28	5194.57
	binder	0.31	15.59	5298.72
	base	1.31	65.50	22236.27
	subbase	4.53	226.50	76705.89
Station: 17+050.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	734.08	39439.95	2906704.12
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.00	0.00	3073902.85
	topeka	0.31	15.28	5209.85
	binder	0.31	15.59	5314.31
	base	1.31	65.50	22301.77
	subbase	4.53	226.50	76932.39

Station: 17+100.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	665.44	34987.88	2941692.00
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.00	0.00	3073902.85
	topeka	0.31	15.28	5225.13
	binder	0.31	15.59	5329.90
	base	1.31	65.50	22367.27
	subbase	4.53	226.50	77158.89
Station: 17+150.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	617.48	32073.04	2973765.03
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.00	0.00	3073902.85
	topeka	0.31	15.28	5240.42
	binder	0.31	15.59	5345.50
	base	1.31	65.50	22432.77
	subbase	4.53	226.50	77385.39
Station: 17+200.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	560.64	29453.18	3003218.21
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.00	0.00	3073902.85
	topeka	0.31	15.28	5255.70
	binder	0.31	15.59	5361.09
	base	1.31	65.50	22498.27
	subbase	4.53	226.50	77611.89
Station: 17+250.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	510.54	26779.68	3029997.89
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.00	0.00	3073902.85
	topeka	0.31	15.28	5270.98
	binder	0.31	15.59	5376.68
	base	1.31	65.50	22563.77
	subbase	4.53	226.50	77838.39
Station: 17+300.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	498.98	25238.20	3055236.09
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.00	0.00	3073902.85
	topeka	0.31	15.28	5286.26
	binder	0.31	15.59	5392.28
	base	1.31	65.50	22629.27
	subbase	4.53	226.50	78064.89
Station: 17+350.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	403.44	22560.49	3077796.58
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.00	0.00	3073902.85
	topeka	0.31	15.28	5301.54
	binder	0.31	15.59	5407.87
	base	1.31	65.50	22694.77
	subbase	4.53	226.50	78291.39
Station: 17+400.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	251.55	16374.77	3094171.35

	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.00	0.00	3073902.85
	topeka	0.31	15.28	5316.82
	binder	0.31	15.59	5423.47
	base	1.31	65.50	22760.27
	subbase	4.53	226.50	78517.89
Station: 17+450.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	92.59	8603.59	3102774.94
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.00	0.00	3073902.85
	topeka	0.31	15.28	5332.10
	binder	0.31	15.59	5439.06
	base	1.31	65.50	22825.77
	subbase	4.53	226.50	78744.39
Station: 17+500.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	6.94	2488.25	3105263.19
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.00	0.00	3073902.85
	topeka	0.31	15.28	5347.38
	binder	0.31	15.59	5454.65
	base	1.31	65.50	22891.27
	subbase	4.53	226.50	78970.89
Station: 17+550.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	0.00	173.51	3105436.70
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	51.51	1287.67	3075190.52
	topeka	0.31	15.28	5362.67
	binder	0.31	15.59	5470.25
	base	1.31	65.50	22956.77
	subbase	4.53	226.50	79197.39
Station: 17+600.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	23.52	587.93	3106024.63
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.00	1287.67	3076478.19
	topeka	0.31	15.28	5377.95
	binder	0.31	15.59	5485.84
	base	1.31	65.50	23022.27
	subbase	4.53	226.50	79423.89
Station: 17+650.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	119.61	3578.17	3109602.80
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.00	0.00	3076478.19
	topeka	0.31	15.28	5393.23
	binder	0.31	15.59	5501.43
	base	1.31	65.50	23087.77
	subbase	4.53	226.50	79650.39
Station: 17+700.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	313.86	10836.68	3120439.48
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.00	0.00	3076478.19
	topeka	0.31	15.28	5408.51

	binder	0.31	15.59	5517.03
	base	1.31	65.50	23153.27
	subbase	4.53	226.50	79876.89
Station: 17+750.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	583.04	22422.37	3142861.85
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.00	0.00	3076478.19
	topeka	0.31	15.28	5423.79
	binder	0.31	15.59	5532.62
	base	1.31	65.50	23218.77
	subbase	4.53	226.50	80103.39
Station: 17+800.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	614.85	29947.21	3172809.06
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.00	0.00	3076478.19
	topeka	0.31	15.28	5439.07
	binder	0.31	15.59	5548.22
	base	1.31	65.50	23284.27
	subbase	4.53	226.50	80329.89
Station: 17+850.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	394.17	25225.43	3198034.48
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.00	0.00	3076478.19
	topeka	0.31	15.28	5454.35
	binder	0.31	15.59	5563.81
	base	1.31	65.50	23349.77
	subbase	4.53	226.50	80556.39
Station: 17+900.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	56.76	11273.24	3209307.72
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.00	0.00	3076478.19
	topeka	0.31	15.28	5469.63
	binder	0.31	15.59	5579.40
	base	1.31	65.50	23415.27
	subbase	4.53	226.50	80782.89
Station: 17+950.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	0.00	1419.12	3210726.85
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	94.09	2352.33	3078830.52
	topeka	0.31	15.28	5484.92
	binder	0.31	15.59	5595.00
	base	1.31	65.50	23480.77
	subbase	4.53	226.50	81009.39
Station: 18+000.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	0.00	0.03	3210726.87
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	235.69	8244.50	3087075.02
	topeka	0.31	15.28	5500.20
	binder	0.31	15.59	5610.59
	base	1.31	65.50	23546.27

	subbase	4.53	226.50	81235.89
Station: 18+050.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	0.00	0.00	3210726.88
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	197.46	10828.55	3097903.56
	topeka	0.31	15.28	5515.48
	binder	0.31	15.59	5626.18
	base	1.31	65.50	23611.77
	subbase	4.53	226.50	81462.39
Station: 18+100.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	0.00	0.00	3210726.88
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	108.13	7639.70	3105543.26
	topeka	0.31	15.28	5530.76
	binder	0.31	15.59	5641.78
	base	1.31	65.50	23677.27
	subbase	4.53	226.50	81688.89
Station: 18+150.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	35.94	898.47	3211625.35
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.00	2703.41	3108246.68
	topeka	0.31	15.28	5546.04
	binder	0.31	15.59	5657.37
	base	1.31	65.50	23742.77
	subbase	4.53	226.50	81915.39
Station: 18+200.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	290.38	8158.07	3219783.42
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.00	0.10	3108246.78
	topeka	0.31	15.28	5561.32
	binder	0.31	15.59	5672.97
	base	1.31	65.50	23808.27
	subbase	4.53	226.50	82141.89
Station: 18+250.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	411.88	17556.51	3237339.93
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.00	0.00	3108246.78
	topeka	0.31	15.28	5576.60
	binder	0.31	15.59	5688.56
	base	1.31	65.50	23873.77
	subbase	4.53	226.50	82368.39
Station: 18+300.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	589.93	25045.24	3262385.17
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.00	0.00	3108246.79
	topeka	0.31	15.28	5591.88
	binder	0.31	15.59	5704.15
	base	1.31	65.50	23939.27
	subbase	4.53	226.50	82594.89
Station: 18+350.000				

	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	246.67	20915.05	3283300.22
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.00	0.00	3108246.79
	topeka	0.31	15.28	5607.17
	binder	0.31	15.59	5719.75
	base	1.31	65.50	24004.77
	subbase	4.53	226.50	82821.39
Station: 18+400.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	0.00	6166.71	3289466.93
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	188.40	4710.11	3112956.90
	topeka	0.31	15.28	5622.45
	binder	0.31	15.59	5735.34
	base	1.31	65.50	24070.27
	subbase	4.53	226.50	83047.89
Station: 18+450.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	0.00	0.00	3289466.93
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	337.14	13138.62	3126095.51
	topeka	0.31	15.28	5637.73
	binder	0.31	15.59	5750.93
	base	1.31	65.50	24135.77
	subbase	4.53	226.50	83274.39
Station: 18+500.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	0.00	0.00	3289466.93
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	500.99	20953.29	3147048.81
	topeka	0.31	15.28	5653.01
	binder	0.31	15.59	5766.53
	base	1.31	65.50	24201.27
	subbase	4.53	226.50	83500.89
Station: 18+550.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	0.03	0.64	3289467.57
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	523.48	25611.73	3172660.53
	topeka	0.31	15.28	5668.29
	binder	0.31	15.59	5782.12
	base	1.31	65.50	24266.77
	subbase	4.53	226.50	83727.39
Station: 18+600.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	0.00	0.64	3289468.21
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	602.17	28141.25	3200801.78
	topeka	0.31	15.28	5683.57
	binder	0.31	15.59	5797.72
	base	1.31	65.50	24332.27
	subbase	4.53	226.50	83953.89
Station: 18+650.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	0.00	0.00	3289468.21
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	629.59	30793.95	3231595.73

	topeka	0.31	15.28	5698.85
	binder	0.31	15.59	5813.31
	base	1.31	65.50	24397.77
	subbase	4.53	226.50	84180.39
Station: 18+700.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	0.00	0.00	3289468.21
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	528.69	28956.86	3260552.59
	topeka	0.31	15.28	5714.13
	binder	0.31	15.59	5828.90
	base	1.31	65.50	24463.27
	subbase	4.53	226.50	84406.89
Station: 18+750.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	0.00	0.00	3289468.21
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	205.55	18355.98	3278908.57
	topeka	0.31	15.28	5729.42
	binder	0.31	15.59	5844.50
	base	1.31	65.50	24528.77
	subbase	4.53	226.50	84633.39
Station: 18+800.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	82.63	2065.79	3291534.01
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.00	5138.77	3284047.33
	topeka	0.31	15.28	5744.70
	binder	0.31	15.59	5860.09
	base	1.31	65.50	24594.27
	subbase	4.53	226.50	84859.89
Station: 18+850.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	168.91	6288.55	3297822.56
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.00	0.00	3284047.33
	topeka	0.31	15.28	5759.98
	binder	0.31	15.59	5875.68
	base	1.31	65.50	24659.77
	subbase	4.53	226.50	85086.39
Station: 18+900.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	21.37	4756.99	3302579.55
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	1.02	25.54	3284072.87
	topeka	0.31	15.28	5775.26
	binder	0.31	15.59	5891.28
	base	1.31	65.50	24725.27
	subbase	4.53	226.50	85312.89
Station: 18+950.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	0.00	534.23	3303113.78
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	126.64	3191.49	3287264.36
	topeka	0.31	15.28	5790.54
	binder	0.31	15.59	5906.87

	base	1.31	65.50	24790.77
	subbase	4.53	226.50	85539.39
Station: 19+000.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	0.00	0.00	3303113.78
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	291.56	10454.95	3297719.31
	topeka	0.31	15.28	5805.82
	binder	0.31	15.59	5922.47
	base	1.31	65.50	24856.27
	subbase	4.53	226.50	85765.89
Station: 19+050.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	0.00	0.00	3303113.78
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	299.61	14779.21	3312498.52
	topeka	0.31	15.28	5821.10
	binder	0.31	15.59	5938.06
	base	1.31	65.50	24921.77
	subbase	4.53	226.50	85992.39
Station: 19+100.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	0.00	0.00	3303113.78
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	205.39	12624.96	3325123.48
	topeka	0.31	15.28	5836.38
	binder	0.31	15.59	5953.65
	base	1.31	65.50	24987.27
	subbase	4.53	226.50	86218.89
Station: 19+150.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	0.00	0.00	3303113.78
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	102.95	7708.42	3332831.90
	topeka	0.31	15.28	5851.67
	binder	0.31	15.59	5969.25
	base	1.31	65.50	25052.77
	subbase	4.53	226.50	86445.39
Station: 19+200.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	0.00	0.00	3303113.78
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	40.23	3579.31	3336411.21
	topeka	0.31	15.28	5866.95
	binder	0.31	15.59	5984.84
	base	1.31	65.50	25118.27
	subbase	4.53	226.50	86671.89
Station: 19+250.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	2.99	74.83	3303188.61
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	3.77	1099.80	3337511.00
	topeka	0.31	15.28	5882.23
	binder	0.31	15.59	6000.43
	base	1.31	65.50	25183.77
	subbase	4.53	226.50	86898.39

Station: 19+300.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	36.86	996.37	3304184.98
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.00	94.17	3337605.17
	topeka	0.31	15.28	5897.51
	binder	0.31	15.59	6016.03
	base	1.31	65.50	25249.27
	subbase	4.53	226.50	87124.89
Station: 19+350.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	73.97	2770.70	3306955.68
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.00	0.01	3337605.18
	topeka	0.31	15.28	5912.79
	binder	0.31	15.59	6031.62
	base	1.31	65.50	25314.77
	subbase	4.53	226.50	87351.39
Station: 19+400.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	118.38	4808.65	3311764.33
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.00	0.01	3337605.20
	topeka	0.31	15.28	5928.07
	binder	0.31	15.59	6047.22
	base	1.31	65.50	25380.27
	subbase	4.53	226.50	87577.89
Station: 19+450.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	204.48	8071.60	3319835.93
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.00	0.00	3337605.20
	topeka	0.31	15.28	5943.35
	binder	0.31	15.59	6062.81
	base	1.31	65.50	25445.77
	subbase	4.53	226.50	87804.39
Station: 19+500.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	263.32	11694.99	3331530.92
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.00	0.00	3337605.20
	topeka	0.31	15.28	5958.63
	binder	0.31	15.59	6078.40
	base	1.31	65.50	25511.27
	subbase	4.53	226.50	88030.89
Station: 19+550.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	282.64	13648.79	3345179.70
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.00	0.00	3337605.20
	topeka	0.31	15.28	5973.92
	binder	0.31	15.59	6094.00
	base	1.31	65.50	25576.77
	subbase	4.53	226.50	88257.39
Station: 19+600.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	249.81	13311.14	3358490.84

	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.00	0.00	3337605.20
	topeka	0.31	15.28	5989.20
	binder	0.31	15.59	6109.59
	base	1.31	65.50	25642.27
	subbase	4.53	226.50	88483.89
Station: 19+650.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	226.99	11919.96	3370410.80
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.00	0.00	3337605.20
	topeka	0.31	15.28	6004.48
	binder	0.31	15.59	6125.18
	base	1.31	65.50	25707.77
	subbase	4.53	226.50	88710.39
Station: 19+700.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	238.77	11644.07	3382054.87
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.00	0.00	3337605.20
	topeka	0.31	15.28	6019.76
	binder	0.31	15.59	6140.78
	base	1.31	65.50	25773.27
	subbase	4.53	226.50	88936.89
Station: 19+750.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	293.58	13308.92	3395363.79
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.00	0.03	3337605.23
	topeka	0.31	15.28	6035.04
	binder	0.31	15.59	6156.37
	base	1.31	65.50	25838.77
	subbase	4.53	226.50	89163.39
Station: 19+800.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	371.76	16633.69	3411997.48
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.00	0.03	3337605.25
	topeka	0.31	15.28	6050.32
	binder	0.31	15.59	6171.97
	base	1.31	65.50	25904.27
	subbase	4.53	226.50	89389.89
Station: 19+850.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	471.64	21085.17	3433082.65
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.00	0.00	3337605.25
	topeka	0.31	15.28	6065.60
	binder	0.31	15.59	6187.56
	base	1.31	65.50	25969.77
	subbase	4.53	226.50	89616.39
Station: 19+900.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	584.82	26411.53	3459494.18
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.00	0.00	3337605.25
	topeka	0.31	15.28	6080.88

	binder	0.31	15.59	6203.15
	base	1.31	65.50	26035.27
	subbase	4.53	226.50	89842.89
Station: 19+950.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	547.85	28316.70	3487810.87
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.00	0.00	3337605.25
	topeka	0.31	15.28	6096.17
	binder	0.31	15.59	6218.75
	base	1.31	65.50	26100.77
	subbase	4.53	226.50	90069.39
Station: 20+000.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	429.99	24446.02	3512256.90
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.00	0.00	3337605.25
	topeka	0.31	15.28	6111.45
	binder	0.31	15.59	6234.34
	base	1.31	65.50	26166.27
	subbase	4.53	226.50	90295.89
Station: 20+050.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	223.55	16338.68	3528595.57
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.03	0.69	3337605.94
	topeka	0.31	15.28	6126.73
	binder	0.31	15.59	6249.93
	base	1.31	65.50	26231.77
	subbase	4.53	226.50	90522.39
Station: 20+100.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	97.17	8018.02	3536613.60
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.00	0.69	3337606.63
	topeka	0.31	15.28	6142.01
	binder	0.31	15.59	6265.53
	base	1.31	65.50	26297.27
	subbase	4.53	226.50	90748.89
Station: 20+150.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	12.73	2747.35	3539360.95
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.00	0.00	3337606.63
	topeka	0.31	15.28	6157.29
	binder	0.31	15.59	6281.12
	base	1.31	65.50	26362.77
	subbase	4.53	226.50	90975.39
Station: 20+200.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	0.00	318.20	3539679.15
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	68.37	1709.23	3339315.87
	topeka	0.31	15.28	6172.57
	binder	0.31	15.59	6296.72
	base	1.31	65.50	26428.27

	subbase	4.53	226.50	91201.89
Station: 20+250.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	0.00	0.01	3539679.16
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	32.25	2515.54	3341831.41
	topeka	0.31	15.28	6187.85
	binder	0.31	15.59	6312.31
	base	1.31	65.50	26493.77
	subbase	4.53	226.50	91428.39
Station: 20+300.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	0.00	0.01	3539679.17
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	10.78	1075.91	3342907.32
	topeka	0.31	15.28	6203.13
	binder	0.31	15.59	6327.90
	base	1.31	65.50	26559.27
	subbase	4.53	226.50	91654.89
Station: 20+350.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	37.14	928.38	3540607.56
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.00	269.60	3343176.92
	topeka	0.31	15.28	6218.42
	binder	0.31	15.59	6343.50
	base	1.31	65.50	26624.77
	subbase	4.53	226.50	91881.39
Station: 20+400.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	48.43	2139.02	3542746.57
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.00	0.00	3343176.92
	topeka	0.31	15.28	6233.70
	binder	0.31	15.59	6359.09
	base	1.31	65.50	26690.27
	subbase	4.53	226.50	92107.89
Station: 20+450.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	24.89	1832.76	3544579.34
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.00	0.00	3343176.92
	topeka	0.31	15.28	6248.98
	binder	0.31	15.59	6374.68
	base	1.31	65.50	26755.77
	subbase	4.53	226.50	92334.39
Station: 20+500.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	0.00	622.13	3545201.47
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	47.43	1185.66	3344362.58
	topeka	0.31	15.28	6264.26
	binder	0.31	15.59	6390.28
	base	1.31	65.50	26821.27
	subbase	4.53	226.50	92560.89
Station: 20+550.000				

	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	0.00	0.00	3545201.47
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	141.41	4720.97	3349083.55
	topeka	0.31	15.28	6279.54
	binder	0.31	15.59	6405.87
	base	1.31	65.50	26886.77
	subbase	4.53	226.50	92787.39
Station: 20+600.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	0.00	0.00	3545201.47
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	176.91	7958.12	3357041.67
	topeka	0.31	15.28	6294.82
	binder	0.31	15.59	6421.47
	base	1.31	65.50	26952.27
	subbase	4.53	226.50	93013.89
Station: 20+650.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	0.00	0.00	3545201.47
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	171.99	8722.50	3365764.17
	topeka	0.31	15.28	6310.10
	binder	0.31	15.59	6437.06
	base	1.31	65.50	27017.77
	subbase	4.53	226.50	93240.39
Station: 20+700.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	0.00	0.00	3545201.47
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	155.22	8180.16	3373944.33
	topeka	0.31	15.28	6325.38
	binder	0.31	15.59	6452.65
	base	1.31	65.50	27083.27
	subbase	4.53	226.50	93466.89
Station: 20+750.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	0.00	0.00	3545201.47
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	139.89	7377.61	3381321.94
	topeka	0.31	15.28	6340.67
	binder	0.31	15.59	6468.25
	base	1.31	65.50	27148.77
	subbase	4.53	226.50	93693.39
Station: 20+800.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	0.00	0.00	3545201.47
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	128.16	6701.09	3388023.03
	topeka	0.31	15.28	6355.95
	binder	0.31	15.59	6483.84
	base	1.31	65.50	27214.27
	subbase	4.53	226.50	93919.89
Station: 20+850.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	0.00	0.00	3545201.47
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	165.88	7350.98	3395374.02

	topeka	0.31	15.28	6371.23
	binder	0.31	15.59	6499.43
	base	1.31	65.50	27279.77
	subbase	4.53	226.50	94146.39
Station: 20+900.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	0.00	0.00	3545201.47
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	187.04	8823.11	3404197.13
	topeka	0.31	15.28	6386.51
	binder	0.31	15.59	6515.03
	base	1.31	65.50	27345.27
	subbase	4.53	226.50	94372.89
Station: 20+950.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	0.00	0.00	3545201.47
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	176.38	9085.65	3413282.78
	topeka	0.31	15.28	6401.79
	binder	0.31	15.59	6530.62
	base	1.31	65.50	27410.77
	subbase	4.53	226.50	94599.39
Station: 21+000.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	0.00	0.00	3545201.47
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	207.43	9595.28	3422878.06
	topeka	0.31	15.28	6417.07
	binder	0.31	15.59	6546.22
	base	1.31	65.50	27476.27
	subbase	4.53	226.50	94825.89
Station: 21+050.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	0.00	0.00	3545201.47
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	249.83	11431.40	3434309.46
	topeka	0.31	15.28	6432.35
	binder	0.31	15.59	6561.81
	base	1.31	65.50	27541.77
	subbase	4.53	226.50	95052.39
Station: 21+100.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	0.00	0.00	3545201.47
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	260.52	12758.64	3447068.10
	topeka	0.31	15.28	6447.63
	binder	0.31	15.59	6577.40
	base	1.31	65.50	27607.27
	subbase	4.53	226.50	95278.89
Station: 21+150.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	0.00	0.05	3545201.52
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	261.94	13061.36	3460129.46
	topeka	0.31	15.28	6462.92
	binder	0.31	15.59	6593.00

	base	1.31	65.50	27672.77
	subbase	4.53	226.50	95505.39
Station: 21+200.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	0.00	0.05	3545201.57
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	278.90	13520.99	3473650.45
	topeka	0.31	15.28	6478.20
	binder	0.31	15.59	6608.59
	base	1.31	65.50	27738.27
	subbase	4.53	226.50	95731.89
Station: 21+250.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	0.00	0.00	3545201.57
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	276.59	13887.25	3487537.70
	topeka	0.31	15.28	6493.48
	binder	0.31	15.59	6624.18
	base	1.31	65.50	27803.77
	subbase	4.53	226.50	95958.39
Station: 21+300.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	0.00	0.00	3545201.57
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	278.50	13877.23	3501414.93
	topeka	0.31	15.28	6508.76
	binder	0.31	15.59	6639.78
	base	1.31	65.50	27869.27
	subbase	4.53	226.50	96184.89
Station: 21+350.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	0.00	0.00	3545201.57
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	378.52	16425.47	3517840.40
	topeka	0.31	15.28	6524.04
	binder	0.31	15.59	6655.37
	base	1.31	65.50	27934.77
	subbase	4.53	226.50	96411.39
Station: 21+400.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	0.00	0.00	3545201.57
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	304.12	17065.87	3534906.27
	topeka	0.31	15.28	6539.32
	binder	0.31	15.59	6670.97
	base	1.31	65.50	28000.27
	subbase	4.53	226.50	96637.89
Station: 21+450.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	0.06	1.53	3545203.10
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	129.51	10840.63	3545746.89
	topeka	0.31	15.28	6554.60
	binder	0.31	15.59	6686.56
	base	1.31	65.50	28065.77
	subbase	4.53	226.50	96864.39

Station: 21+500.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	0.00	1.53	3545204.63
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	137.20	6667.73	3552414.62
	topeka	0.31	15.28	6569.88
	binder	0.31	15.59	6702.15
	base	1.31	65.50	28131.27
	subbase	4.53	226.50	97090.89
Station: 21+550.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	0.00	0.00	3545204.63
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	143.63	7020.91	3559435.53
	topeka	0.31	15.28	6585.17
	binder	0.31	15.59	6717.75
	base	1.31	65.50	28196.77
	subbase	4.53	226.50	97317.39
Station: 21+600.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	0.00	0.00	3545204.63
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	158.47	7552.51	3566988.04
	topeka	0.31	15.28	6600.45
	binder	0.31	15.59	6733.34
	base	1.31	65.50	28262.27
	subbase	4.53	226.50	97543.89
Station: 21+650.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	0.00	0.00	3545204.63
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	233.85	9807.94	3576795.98
	topeka	0.31	15.28	6615.73
	binder	0.31	15.59	6748.93
	base	1.31	65.50	28327.77
	subbase	4.53	226.50	97770.39
Station: 21+700.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	0.00	0.00	3545204.63
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	323.24	13927.30	3590723.28
	topeka	0.31	15.28	6631.01
	binder	0.31	15.59	6764.53
	base	1.31	65.50	28393.27
	subbase	4.53	226.50	97996.89
Station: 21+750.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	0.00	0.00	3545204.63
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	413.59	18420.75	3609144.03
	topeka	0.31	15.28	6646.29
	binder	0.31	15.59	6780.12
	base	1.31	65.50	28458.77
	subbase	4.53	226.50	98223.39
Station: 21+800.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	0.00	0.00	3545204.63

	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	482.20	22394.71	3631538.74
	topeka	0.31	15.28	6661.57
	binder	0.31	15.59	6795.72
	base	1.31	65.50	28524.27
	subbase	4.53	226.50	98449.89
Station: 21+850.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	0.00	0.00	3545204.63
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	579.03	26530.65	3658069.39
	topeka	0.31	15.28	6676.85
	binder	0.31	15.59	6811.31
	base	1.31	65.50	28589.77
	subbase	4.53	226.50	98676.39
Station: 21+900.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	0.00	0.00	3545204.63
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	531.08	27752.74	3685822.13
	topeka	0.31	15.28	6692.13
	binder	0.31	15.59	6826.90
	base	1.31	65.50	28655.27
	subbase	4.53	226.50	98902.89
Station: 21+950.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	0.05	1.20	3545205.83
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	537.44	26713.10	3712535.24
	topeka	0.31	15.28	6707.42
	binder	0.31	15.59	6842.50
	base	1.31	65.50	28720.77
	subbase	4.53	226.50	99129.39
Station: 22+000.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	0.00	1.20	3545207.03
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	673.58	30275.42	3742810.66
	topeka	0.31	15.28	6722.70
	binder	0.31	15.59	6858.09
	base	1.31	65.50	28786.27
	subbase	4.53	226.50	99355.89
Station: 22+050.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	0.00	0.00	3545207.03
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	550.79	30609.08	3773419.74
	topeka	0.31	15.28	6737.98
	binder	0.31	15.59	6873.68
	base	1.31	65.50	28851.77
	subbase	4.53	226.50	99582.39
Station: 22+100.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	0.00	0.00	3545207.03
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	400.07	23771.33	3797191.06
	topeka	0.31	15.28	6753.26

	binder	0.31	15.59	6889.28
	base	1.31	65.50	28917.27
	subbase	4.53	226.50	99808.89
Station: 22+150.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	0.01	0.26	3545207.29
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	437.43	20937.48	3818128.54
	topeka	0.31	15.28	6768.54
	binder	0.31	15.59	6904.87
	base	1.31	65.50	28982.77
	subbase	4.53	226.50	100035.39
Station: 22+200.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	0.00	0.26	3545207.55
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	491.69	23228.13	3841356.67
	topeka	0.31	15.28	6783.82
	binder	0.31	15.59	6920.47
	base	1.31	65.50	29048.27
	subbase	4.53	226.50	100261.89
Station: 22+250.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	0.00	0.00	3545207.55
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	507.41	24977.60	3866334.27
	topeka	0.31	15.28	6799.10
	binder	0.31	15.59	6936.06
	base	1.31	65.50	29113.77
	subbase	4.53	226.50	100488.39
Station: 22+300.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	0.00	0.00	3545207.55
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	452.81	24005.68	3890339.95
	topeka	0.31	15.28	6814.38
	binder	0.31	15.59	6951.65
	base	1.31	65.50	29179.27
	subbase	4.53	226.50	100714.89
Station: 22+350.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	0.00	0.00	3545207.55
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	572.57	25634.72	3915974.68
	topeka	0.31	15.28	6829.67
	binder	0.31	15.59	6967.25
	base	1.31	65.50	29244.77
	subbase	4.53	226.50	100941.39
Station: 22+400.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	0.00	0.00	3545207.55
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	415.27	24696.15	3940670.82
	topeka	0.31	15.28	6844.95
	binder	0.31	15.59	6982.84
	base	1.31	65.50	29310.27

	subbase	4.53	226.50	101167.89
Station: 22+450.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	0.00	0.00	3545207.55
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	197.19	15311.49	3955982.32
	topeka	0.31	15.28	6860.23
	binder	0.31	15.59	6998.43
	base	1.31	65.50	29375.77
	subbase	4.53	226.50	101394.39
Station: 22+500.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	0.00	0.00	3545207.55
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	23.54	5518.21	3961500.52
	topeka	0.31	15.28	6875.51
	binder	0.31	15.59	7014.03
	base	1.31	65.50	29441.27
	subbase	4.53	226.50	101620.89
Station: 22+550.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	114.15	2853.71	3548061.27
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.00	588.55	3962089.07
	topeka	0.31	15.28	6890.79
	binder	0.31	15.59	7029.62
	base	1.31	65.50	29506.77
	subbase	4.53	226.50	101847.39
Station: 22+600.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	394.50	12716.23	3560777.50
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.00	0.05	3962089.12
	topeka	0.31	15.28	6906.07
	binder	0.31	15.59	7045.22
	base	1.31	65.50	29572.27
	subbase	4.53	226.50	102073.89
Station: 22+650.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	194.98	14737.05	3575514.54
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.00	0.00	3962089.12
	topeka	0.31	15.28	6921.35
	binder	0.31	15.59	7060.81
	base	1.31	65.50	29637.77
	subbase	4.53	226.50	102300.39
Station: 22+700.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	0.00	4874.53	3580389.07
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	19.30	482.55	3962571.68
	topeka	0.31	15.28	6936.63
	binder	0.31	15.59	7076.40
	base	1.31	65.50	29703.27
	subbase	4.53	226.50	102526.89
Station: 22+750.000				

	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	0.00	0.00	3580389.07
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	37.85	1428.71	3964000.39
	topeka	0.31	15.28	6951.92
	binder	0.31	15.59	7092.00
	base	1.31	65.50	29768.77
	subbase	4.53	226.50	102753.39
Station: 22+800.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	3.04	76.04	3580465.11
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	2.53	1009.40	3965009.79
	topeka	0.31	15.28	6967.20
	binder	0.31	15.59	7107.59
	base	1.31	65.50	29834.27
	subbase	4.53	226.50	102979.89
Station: 22+850.000				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	9.80	320.93	3580786.04
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.02	63.83	3965073.62
	topeka	0.31	15.28	6982.48
	binder	0.31	15.59	7123.18
	base	1.31	65.50	29899.77
	subbase	4.53	226.50	103206.39
Station: 22+869.084				
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Cut)	13.95	226.54	3581012.58
	hajme khaki_subgrade(Fill)	0.00	0.23	3965073.85
	topeka	0.31	5.83	6988.31
	binder	0.31	5.95	7129.14
	base	1.31	25.00	29924.77
	subbase	4.53	86.45	103292.85